

PROGRESS REPORT FLAGSHIP PROJECT H2Mobility SPOKE 1- Progress Report _ III semester

SPOKE 1 – Aerospace and sustainable mobility
Flagship Project – H2Mobility

Progress Report

NODES - Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

PROGRESS REPORT FLAGSHIP PROJECT H2Mobility

SPOKE 1- Progress Report _ III semester

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.

Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.
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1. EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

1.1 Objectives

The main objective of H2Mobility is to contribute to improve the technological readiness to the exploitation of H₂ as the renewable energy vector for the future mobility system. This goal will determine a strong demand for new technologies, new components, and innovative services for green H₂ storage (adsorbing and absorbing materials) and its subsequent distribution and use to provide energy on-demand (fuel cells, internal combustion engines). The activities include the use of robust and established technology pathways to produce system to store (e.g. adsorption and absorption in different matrices, chemical storage), to distribute and to use (fuel cells, internal combustion engines) green hydrogen. This implies innovation activities for the development of new solutions for components and subsystems in order to lower costs, fostering the market acceptance and supporting the creation of local supply chains.

Beside H₂ storage, distribution and use capabilities, the project will also address E-Fuels. In this regard, the research activity will focus mainly on the development of components, technologies and systems for conversion of CO₂ and other vectors into RFNBO (Renewable Fuels of Non-Biological Origin) in order to optimize bio-catalytic conversion, with the aim to exploit specific and optimized metabolic pathways. Additionally, the environmental benefits of producing and using RFNBO will be quantified according to LCA based methodology, as per the REDII and ICAO-CORSIA

1.2 Explanation of the work carried out per RM in the reporting period

1.2.1 Research Module 1

Research Module n. 1:	Start month: M1	End month: M36					
Title: Hydrogen production							
Location in Mezzogiorno: N							
RM Leader	POLITO						
Partners involved	Envipark	UNITO					
Type of action:	Industrial Research						
Effort in person/months:	POLITO:	4,86	Envipark:	1,13	UNITO:	0,114	
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):							
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Hydrogen production through electrical-based pathway: water electrolysis 2) Bio-based processes for H₂ production and aqueous phase reforming as alternative approaches of green H₂ production 							
Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):							

1) Objective1/ Hydrogen production through electrical-based pathway: water electrolysis

Task 1.1 Technology briefs on Green Hydrogen generation by electrolysis (POLITO DENERG; ENVIPARK)

During the first semester of the second year, the technology brief for SOEC electrolysis has been completed for what concerns the status of the technology. The analysis of the current status and projections of performance and costs is ongoing, together with the assessment of potential and barriers for alkaline and PEM technologies. The technology briefs for low-temperature anion exchange membranes (AEM) electrolyzers and intermediate-temperature proton conducting electrolyzers are under elaboration. In the following lines, the main results are summarized.

Solid Oxide Electrolyzers

SOE technology is at a pre-commercial stage of development on the small-medium size. SOE electrolyzers are based on solid electrolytes (typically Yttria-Stabilized Zirconium (YSZ)) that require high temperature (700-900 °C) to conduct the oxygen ions. Due to the high temperature, SOE exploits steam instead of liquid water to convert H₂O into gaseous hydrogen. The cell is composed by an air electrode based on a ceramic oxide (e.g. Lanthanum Strontium Cobalt Ferrite (LSCF)) and a hydrogen electrode usually composed by YSZ and Nickel. A barrier layer (e.g. Yttria-Doped Ceria (YDC)) is included between electrolyte and anode to guarantee thermal compatibility between the layers. Separation between electrodes is made by steel interconnectors. Gas leakages are avoided by a glass sealant.

Precious metals are not required as catalysts, thanks to the high-temperature operation that enhances the kinetics of the reaction. SOE cells are also highly flexible towards the presence of carbon-containing molecules at the electrodes, being even able to perform the co-electrolysis of H₂O and CO₂. Even if the cells are not negatively affected by the presence of CO₂, the purity of the hydrogen produced is guaranteed only using a pure water steam input.

SOE electrolyzers are the most electrically efficient technology thanks to the fact that they operate at high temperatures, at which the electricity component of the electrolysis reaction can be progressively substituted with heat. Thus, considering conversion from electricity to hydrogen only, higher efficiencies are the result (75-85%). In SOE cells, the endothermicity of the water splitting reaction is balanced by the Joule heating of the cell at reasonable levels of current density, while the low-temperature cells operate always in an exothermic regime. Thanks to this, the SOE cell and stacks can operate at a point defined as thermo-neutral, in which the heat generated by polarization losses is able to balance the endothermicity of the reaction. By operating at a current density slightly higher than the thermo-neutral value, an SOE stack can also balance the heat losses towards the ambient. Hence, the operation of an SOE electrolyzer can be performed without the need for heat to maintain the stack at high temperature, having only as thermal requirement the preheating of reactants. If SOE are supplied with steam at high temperature (for example as a by-product from industrial processes, such as in the steel making industry) they can potentially reach 100% conversion from electricity to H₂. Another advantage of SOE is the capability of cells to operate in reverse mode as fuel cells. An electrolyzer can thus be employed also as fuel cell, making SOE ideal for the application in Power-to-Power systems, which are designed to produce hydrogen from excess renewable electricity, to store it and to utilize it in a second time in fuel cells when the electricity demand is exceeding the renewable production.

Figure 1.1.1 – Typical Balance of Plant of SOE system [1]

SOE currently operates at ambient pressure with limited current density ($0.3\text{-}1\text{ A/cm}^2$), but the high-temperature operation allows to achieve a lower voltage ($1.0\text{-}1.5\text{ V}$) compared to low-temperature electrolyzers. The operation in pressure up to $10\text{-}15\text{ bar}$ has been tested only at laboratory level. The typical BoP of a SOE system is shown in Figure 1.1.1.1.1. The BoP is simpler if compared to low-temperature electrolysis systems but requires for heat exchangers and piping the use of expensive materials (eg. Nickel alloys) that can withstand high temperatures in air and steam environments. SOE technology has several disadvantages: thermo-chemical cycling, especially under shutdown/ramping periods, leads to faster degradation and shorter lifetimes. Other issues related to stack degradation include challenges related to sealing; electrode contamination by silica used in the sealants; and other additional contaminant sources (e.g. chromium) from piping, interconnects and sealing. All these aspects lead to a stack lifetime significantly lower compared to low-temperature electrolyzers, and thus an higher cost of the hydrogen produced due to the need of replacing the stack more frequently ($20\text{-}40\text{ khours}$) than alkaline or PEM electrolyzers. SOECs are today only deployed at the kW-scale, although some current demonstration projects have already reached 1 MW .

References

[1] IRENA (2020), *Green Hydrogen Cost Reduction: Scaling up Electrolyzers to Meet the 1.50C Climate Goal*, International Renewable Energy Agency

Task 1.2 Technology development – modeling electrolysis system at SRU/stack level (POLITO DENERG)

The thermo-electrochemical modeling platform previously developed for single cells for intermediate and high-temperature electrolyzers with solid oxide electrolytes has been calibrated at different temperatures for the PCEC application using literature data. The model calibration is summarized in the following lines.

The model has been applied in a 2D domain to simulate a rectangular cell ($\sim 30\text{ cm}^2$ - $6\text{ cm} \times 5\text{ cm}$ active area) operating in counter-flow configuration in the conditions reported in the following figure.

Figure 1.1.2 - 2D PCEC model, cell schematic

In order to calibrate the model, the current-voltage performance of a PCEC cell from the literature has been selected. The cell data presented in the work of Zheng et al. [1] have been selected. In this work, the experimental performance of a PCEC cell at 500°C , 550°C and 600°C is reported. The model has been run in isothermal mode at the three temperatures, and 3 model parameters have been selected as calibration parameters: anodic exchange current density, cathodic exchange current density, electrolyte conductivity. The calibration procedure was successful, and the model proved to be able to replicate the performance of a PCEC in the $500^\circ\text{C}\text{-}600^\circ\text{C}$ temperature range. The results of the calibrated model are reported in the following figure.

Figure 1.2.3 – PCEC cell model calibration. Experimental data from [1]

References

[1] H. Zheng, et al. "Hydrogen production at intermediate temperatures with proton conducting ceramic cells: Electrocatalytic activity, durability and energy efficiency," *Journal of Energy Chemistry*, vol. 86, pp. 437–446, Nov. 2023, doi: 10.1016/J.JECHEM.2023.07.030.

Task 1.3 Technology testing – Test procedures/protocols for electrolyzers and components (POLITO DENERG; ENVIPARK)

The activity that has been performed in this task during the first semester of the second year is the review of standardized protocols and testing infrastructures for testing Proton Exchange Membrane electrolyzers. The summary of the results is provided in the following lines.

Task 1.3.2 review of test protocols for PEM

A review of the main international test protocols for PEM electrolyzers has been performed. The summary of the results is reported.

i. EU harmonized protocols for testing of low temperature water electrolyzers (JRC, 2021)

The "EU harmonized protocols for testing of low temperature water electrolyzers" is a technical report published by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) in 2021 that provides harmonized protocols for assessing the performance and the durability of electrolyzers. The reference document is the following:

European Commission, Joint Research Centre, Tsotridis, G., Pilenga, A., *EU harmonized protocols for testing of low temperature water electrolysis*, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/58880>

The harmonized protocols and methodology allow to improve the repeatability and reproducibility of the test results enhancing their comparability. Moreover, they can boost the representativity of the experimental campaigns in simulating the real-world conditions and applications. Finally, the testing protocols identify specific key performance indices (KPIs) that can be fundamental to assess performance and durability. The JRC report includes a set of operating

conditions, testing protocols and procedure to be applied in order to assess both the performance and the durability of low temperature electrolyzers. The report specifies the detailed methodology to adopt in order to investigate the behaviour of the materials, assess the performance of single cell and short stack and evaluate the operation of the system (i.e., stack and balance of plane (BoP)).

According to the testing protocols, performance and durability of single cell and short stack can be assessed by performing *in-situ tests* over a wide range of operating conditions and monitoring the electrochemical properties. The in-situ testing activity at cell and stack level enable the evaluation of the performance by using a set of indicators that can be derived either as direct experimental results or post-processing the test outcomes. The most frequently used in-situ tests are:

- Polarization curve (I-V curve) for evaluating the overall electrochemical performances
- Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) for identifying the contribution of ohmic, activation and concentration losses and evaluating the reaction rates, the diffusion coefficients and the charge transfer resistance
- Cyclic voltammetry (CV) for measuring the reaction kinetics and determining the electrochemical active surface area.

The detailed methodologies to correctly perform the in-situ tests are described in three specific reports published by JRC:

- i. T. Malkow, A. Pilenga, G. Tsotridis, and G. De Marco, EU harmonised polarization curve test method for low-temperature water electrolysis, EUR 29182 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2018, ISBN 978-92-79-81992-6, doi:10.2760/324006, JRC104045.
- ii. T. Malkow, A. Pilenga, G. Tsotridis, EU harmonised test procedure: electrochemical impedance spectroscopy for water electrolysis cells, EUR 29267 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2018, ISBN 978-92-79-88739-0, doi:10.2760/8984, JRC107053
- iii. T. Malkow, G. De Marco, G. Tsotridis, EU harmonised cyclic voltammetry test method for low temperature water electrolysis single cells, EUR 29285 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2018, ISBN 978-92-79-89871-6, doi:10.2760/140687, JRC111151

In order to carry out the in-situ experimental campaign, the JRC protocol specifies the reference setting value of the different test input parameters (e.g., cell/stack temperature, water inlet temperature, water conductivity, hydrogen and oxygen outlet pressure).

	Test Input Parameters	Unit	Reference Settings
Cell/short stack	Cell/Stack temperature	°C	60
	Water quality (conductivity) at recirculation loop <i>inlet</i>	$\mu\text{S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$	≤ 1.0 ISO 3696 Grade 2 @ 25 °C
ANODE	Water inlet temperature	°C	60
	Water inlet pressure (absolute)	kPa; (bar)	100; (1)
	Water quality (conductivity) <i>within recirculation loop</i>	$\mu\text{S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$	≤ 1.0 ISO 3696 Grade 2 @ 25 °C
	Minimum Water inlet flowrate	$\text{mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$	2.0
	Oxygen outlet pressure (absolute)	kPa; (bar)	100; (1)
CATHODE	Water inlet temperature	°C	60
	Minimum Water inlet flowrate (if applied)	$\text{mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$	2.0
	Hydrogen outlet pressure (abs)	kPa; (bar)	100; (1)

Source: JRC, 2020

Figure 1.3.2.1 – Reference values for Test Input Parameters for PEM testing

The protocol also identifies a set of test output parameters (e.g., cell/stack voltage, hydrogen and oxygen production rate, quality and concentration) to be measured while performing the tests. The operating conditions identified as a reference in the protocols should theoretically represent the center of the normal operating range. However, in some cases, the electrolyzers may be forced to work under operating conditions that are outside of this window.

Figure 1.3.2.2 – Layout of a test facility for PEM electrolyser

In-situ tests can also be carried out on single cell and short stack with the aim of assessing the durability. In this case the real operation history that the electrolyser system will experience during the actual operation has to be translated into time dependent load profiles. This conversion is composed by multiple steps:

- Identification of operational conditions experienced during actual service
- appropriate simulation of these as operation conditions to be imposed in *in-situ* tests on cell or short stack
- establishing the degradation rate (corresponding to the selected performance indicator, usually cell/short stack voltage) through *in-situ* testing

According to the protocols, to simplify execution of in-situ testing for the second step, the actual service conditions are usually simulated by imposing two different time dependent profiles for the electric power supply, namely operation at steady state and dynamic operation according to pre-defined profiles that are representative of transients and dynamic conditions.

ii. DOE-NREL

The HydroGEN consortium is led by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory and includes Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, Sandia National Laboratories, Idaho National Laboratory, and Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory. HydroGEN is funded by DOE's Hydrogen and Fuel Cell Technologies Office in the Office of Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy.

The consortium organizes the "Annual Advanced Water Splitting Technology Pathways Benchmarking and Protocols Workshop" in which member from the industry, the national laboratories and the academia review protocols for testing and benchmarking specific materials and components.

These protocols are not yet harmonized and standardized, but they are posted on the Energy Materials Network Website and published on open access peer-reviewed journals.

iii. NIST

The only testing protocol for electrolysers by NIST was published by B. McCollum et al. in 1927.

iv. ISO TC 197

The Working Group 34 of ISO/TC 197 is responsible for the standardization of "Hydrogen generators using water electrolysis test protocols and safety requirements". In 2019, the ISO/TC 197 published the "ISO 22734:2019 Hydrogen generators using water electrolysis — Industrial, commercial, and residential applications". This document "*defines the construction, safety and performance requirements of modular and factory-matched hydrogen gas generation appliances, herein referred to hydrogen generators, using electrochemical reactions to electrolyte water to produce hydrogen*". The standards defined in this document can be applied to electrolysers that adopt one of the following ion transport medium typologies:

- Group of aqueous bases
- Group of aqueous acid
- Solid polymeric materials with acid function group additions, such as acid proton exchange membrane (PEM)
- Solid polymeric materials with basic function group additions, such as anion exchange membrane (AEM)

This document is applicable to electrolysers intended for industrial and commercial uses and indoor and outdoor residential application. The ISO 22734-2019 defines the standards requirements for:

- the operating conditions
- the risk management
- the mechanical equipment
- the electrical equipment, wiring and ventilation

- the control system
- the ion transport medium
- the protection of service personnel.

The ISO 22734-2019 identifies the tests that have to be performed in order to verify that an electrolyser is compliant with the design specification. According to the standard, the following tests have to be conducted: electrical, pressure, leakage, dilution, protection against the spread of fire, temperature, environmental, performance, spillage, overflow and drain, mechanical strength, stability, vent and sound level.

The standard specifies the basic test arrangement and the reference test conditions to be adopted while performing the testing activity. More in detail, the test should be performed at the factory or at the installation site (if applicable) and while conducting the test the electrolyser system (i.e., stack and BoP with air filters, start-up devices, venting or exhaust systems) has to be installed in accordance with the manufacturer's instruction to replicate the manner in which it has to be installed and operated. As concerns the reference standard conditions, the document provides indications about the environmental conditions (temperature between 15 °C and 35 °C, relative humidity lower than 75%, atmospheric pressure between 75 kPa and 106 kPa, absence of hoarfrost, dew, rain, solar radiation) and the status of the electrolyser (e.g., position, accessories, main supply voltage, duty cycle, loading and filling).

Focusing on the performance tests, the standard specifies to conduct:

- hydrogen and oxygen production rate test: the hydrogen production rate shall be measured at 100% capacity for a period of 1 hour using the method described in ISO 9300, ISO 9951, ISO 10790 or ISO 14511. If applicable for industrial and commercial applications, also the oxygen production rate shall be measured according to the same procedure described for hydrogen. The average production rate has to meet or exceed the rate specified by the manufacture.
- hydrogen and oxygen quality test, the quality of hydrogen and oxygen (when applicable) shall be verified to meet or exceed the manufacturer's specifications. ISO 14687 provides detailed indication on suitable hydrogen quality analysis methods.

Currently, the ISO/TC 197 is developing two standards focused on the testing protocols and guidance:

- ISO/AWI¹ 22734-1 Hydrogen generators using water electrolysis — Industrial, commercial, and residential applications — Part 1: General requirements, test protocols and safety requirements
- ISO/AWI TR² 22734-2 Hydrogen generators using water electrolysis — Part 2: Testing guidance for performing electricity grid service

Task 1.4 Evaluation of r-SOC (reversible Fuel cell) installation in residential and commercial eco-building: permitting procedures, safety aspects for the installation. (POLITO-DENERG)

As a result of the adoption of the MIMIT decree 7/7/2023 that updated the technical regulations on safety in the design, construction, and operation of H2 electrolysis production and storage facilities, an in-depth analysis was carried out on the specific impact of this regulation on reversible SOEFC systems. The adoption of this technical regulation brings to several hotspots that need to be considered in terms of safety and permitting. The main aspects that could affect the implementation of a solution in residential and commercial eco-building are the pressures limits and the related safety distances. In the following table the different distances to be respected from the hazardous elements of an electrolysis facility are described according to the provisions of MIMIT decree 7/7/2023:

Hydrogen operating pressure (barg)	External safety distance	Protection safety distance	Internal safety distance
700 < P ≤ 1000	30	15	15

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¹ AWI: approved work item

² TR: technical report

$500 < P \leq 700$	25	15	15
$300 < P \leq 500$	20	15	15
$100 < P \leq 300$	17	12	12
$50 < P \leq 100$	12	8	8
$30 < P \leq 50$	8	6	6
$10 < P \leq 30$	7	5	5
$P \leq 10$	5	3	3

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... if this regulation represents a significant step forward towards a consistent regulatory framework for hydrogen in Italy, reflects the industrial concept at the bottom of these facilities which hinder systems like the one implemented in Reflex ect for a residential and commercial application to find its proper location. The strict application of the provisions of technical regulation implies distances that are hardly to be respected in urban areas. Indeed, applying the Engineering "reach to fire safety" as per the Ministerial Decree of May 9, 2007, risk assessment can be a valuable tool to achieve ty requirements of Fire Brigade and at the same time to provide a scientific approach that can facilitate the reduction of distances required. Finally, this could a single case approach but a proper distinction among industrial application and residential/commercial ones should be seriously considered by legislator to allow a smooth integration of reversible EFC and the other connected systems also in this type of fields.

... e case of Reflex project, this new regulation was not present at that time, and the only other hydrogen related safety lation in Italy, Decree of 23 October 2018 by the Ministry of the Interior: "Technical rule for fire prevention for the gn, construction, and operation of hydrogen distribution plants for motor vehicles" was not applicable as intended for rogen distribution for mobility purposes. For this reason, a combination of two technical regulations, not hydrogen ed, have been applied to meet safety requirements in a way meaningful for the specific residential and commercial ication of Reflex project. Moreover, the general safety approach was considered: Seveso Directive (not applicable as rogen quantities below the 5 tons) and the Atex Directive for the classification of hazardous zones. The latter has been sidered as the presence of hydrogen implies a certain probability of forming explosive atmospheres.

... mentioned before, two technical regulations related to natural gas have been considered to prove the compliance to safety permitting requirements:

- natural gas storage systems: Decree of the Ministry of the Interior February 3, 2016, "Approval of the technical fire prevention rule for the design, construction, and operation of natural gas deposits with a density not exceeding 0.8 and of biogas deposits, even with a density above 0.8". In this case, the most relevant parameter for safety was the geometric capacity of the storage system. The installation of the hydrogen storage system thus becomes subject to the evaluation of the Fire Brigade if the geometric capacity is greater than 0.75 m3. The considered storage system fell within category 4, as defined by the technical regulation, and therefore the less restrictive in terms of safety requirements;
- Regarding the cogeneration system to be used in the residential context, a technical regulation for cogeneration groups powered by natural gas was also applied in this case: Ministerial Decree July 13, 2011. Regarding the reversible SOEFC system to be installed in Reflex, the technical regulation did not require evaluation by the Fire Brigade Command because the net power produced was less than 25 kW, and therefore the provisions of the decree were considered to comply with standard safety conditions but without the obligation of project evaluation.

The following table is the result of a research activity done through the involvement of Environment Park in HyPOP, a European project funded by the Clean Hydrogen partnership. In this project, an overview of the safety, permitting and certification requirements of hydrogen technologies is under development. The main regulations available and the future developments has been considered.

... e main technical regulations for safety in Italy are divided according to the potential hydrogen technology and the related on activity as defined by D.P.R 1/08/2011 n. 151 (ex DM 16/02/1982).

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Annex I Activities Presidential Decree 151/2011 Hydrogen technology	Hydrogen technology	Technical fire prevention rule (reference D2.1)
Production and plants where flammable and/or oxidizing gases are produced and/or used with total quantities in the preceding 25 cubic meters per hour	Production plants	07/2023: Technical fire prevention rule for the adoption of methodologies for risk analysis and fire measures to be adopted for the design, construction, operation of hydrogen production plants by electrolysis and compressed storage systems; 02/2016: Approval of the technical fire prevention measures for the design, construction, and operation of natural gas facilities with a density not exceeding 0.8 and biogas facilities, even if their density is above 0.8.
Production or decompression plants for flammable and/or oxidizing gases with a capacity > 50 Nm ³ /h and up to 2.4 cubic meters	Production plants	07/2023 (see 1 C); 04/2008: Technical regulation for the design, construction, testing, operation, and monitoring of works and for the distribution and direct lines of natural gas with a density not exceeding 0.8; 04/2008: Technical regulation for the design, construction, testing, operation, and monitoring of works and for the transportation of natural gas with a density not exceeding 0.8.
Production of compressed flammable gases in mobile containers with an overall geometric capacity from 0.75 to 2 cubic meters	Production plants, tube trailers	07/2023 (see 1 C); 02/2016 (see 1 C).
Production of compressed flammable gases in mobile containers with an overall geometric capacity greater than 2 cubic meters	Production plants, tube trailers	07/2023 (see 1 C); 02/2016 (see 1 C).
Production of compressed flammable gases into containers with a total geometric capacity greater than 5 cubic meters	Production plants, bundles or containers	07/2023 (see 1 C); 02/2016 (see 1 C).
Production of compressed flammable gases, in fixed tanks with a total geometric capacity from 0.75 to 2 cubic meters	Production plants, tanks	07/2023 (see 1 C); 02/2016 (see 1 C).
Production of compressed flammable gases, in fixed tanks with a total geometric capacity greater than 2 cubic meters	Production plants, tanks	07/2023 (see 1 C); 02/2016 (see 1 C).
Production and distribution networks for flammable gases, including those of petroleum or chemical origin, with a density < 0.8 and pressure from 0.5 to 2.4 Mpa	Production plants, distribution networks, gas pipelines or gas networks	07/2023 (see 1 C); 04/2008 (see 2B and 2C); 04/2008 (see 2B and 2C).
Production and distribution networks for flammable gases, including those of petroleum or chemical origin, with a density > 2.4 Mpa	Production plants, distribution networks, gas pipelines or gas networks	07/2023 (see 1 C); 04/2008 (see 2B and 2C); 04/2008 (see 2B and 2C).
Production plants for gaseous fuels and mixed type (including gaseous)	Production plants, refueling (HRS)	10/2018: Regola tecnica di prevenzione incendi per la progettazione, costruzione ed esercizio degli impianti di produzione di idrogeno per autotrazione; 05/2002 e decreti associati: Distributori di gas naturali; 04/2012: Distributori a carica lenta di gas naturale; 06/2021, Autotrazione GNL: Distributori di Gas

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		e Liquefatto (GNL) e Gas Naturale Compresso (GNC).
for the production of auxiliary electric power with combustion engines and cogeneration plants of total between 25 kW and 350 kW	ells	/07/2011: Technical rule for fire prevention for allation of internal combustion engines coupled ectric generators or other operating machines and ration units serving civil, industrial, agricultural, al, commercial, and service activities.
for the production of auxiliary electric power with combustion engines and cogeneration plants of total between 350 kW e 700 kW		
for the production of auxiliary electric power with combustion engines and cogeneration plants of total 700 kW		
or heat production fuelled by solid, liquid, or fuel with a capacity greater than 116 kW and up to	ells	/11/2019: Technical fire prevention rule for the construction, and operation of heat production fueled by gaseous fuels.
or heat production fuelled by solid, liquid, or fuel with a capacity greater than 350 kW and up to		
or heat production fuelled by solid, liquid, or fuel with a capacity greater than 700 kW		

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Some of these technical regulations could also be applied for other cases as the ones described in the following research modules as referred to future distribution and transport solutions (e.g FC mobility).

2) Objective2/ Bio-based processes for H2 production and aqueous phase reforming as alternative approaches of green H2 production

Task 1.5 BIO-Electrochemical processes for H2 production (POLITO DISAT)

During the third semester of the project, we investigate the performance of all MFCs implemented and developed by applying optimized bio-anodes, as deeply explained in the previous report. We performed two sets of experiments in the labs. With the first set, we started the investigation of brush-shaped carbon-based electrodes to increase the surface area available for biofilm formation with the main aim to improve the overall performance of these bio-electrochemical devices, as confirmed by Figure 1.5.1a). Regarding this experiment, it is also important to underline that the MFCs devices showed a bottle-shape that recalls the structure of the H-cell selected for MECs and the cathode materials mimic the one of the traditional fuel cells. The employment of brush-shaped carbon-based electrodes ensured an improvement of overall MFCs' performance, leading thus to reach an average voltage output close to (164±24) mV and a maximum current density equal to (603.9 ±35.6) mA m⁻². The good, achieved performance was also confirmed by polarization curves obtained by implementing a Linear Sweep (LSV) Voltammetry characterization. To this purpose, Figure 1.5.1 b) allowed to establish that these devices reached an open circuit voltage (OCV) close to 0.4V and a high short circuit current close to 277.8 A m⁻².

Figure 1.5.1 a) Voltage and current density output for all MFCs whose anodes is made of brush-shaped carbon-based electrode; b) LSV measurements performed on these devices.

The second set explores the decoration of conventional planar carbon-based electrodes, as described in the report of the previous semester. We investigate the optimization of carbon-based electrodes employed in Bio-Electrochemical Systems (BES) by the deposition on commercial carbon paper electrodes of nanostructured layers of poly(3,4-ethylene-dioxy-thiophene) poly(styrene-sulfonate) (PEDOT:PSS) via Ultrasonic Spray Coating (USC), obtained starting from 3 different amount of PEDOT, as represented in Figure 1.5.2.

Figure 1.5.2 Schematic representation of the anodes fabrication by USC process, leading thus to obtain 3 different anodes electrodes differentiated by the content of deposited PEDOT onto carbon based materials.

This innovative application of USC allowed us to demonstrate that uniform and controlled depositions of PEDOT:PSS can be successfully obtained on carbon-based electrodes, leading thus to combine the continuous electrical conductivity of PEDOT:PSS to the porosity of planar carbon-based electrodes. All physic-chemical characterizations employed, including EDX e Raman Spectroscopy, on these samples allowed demonstrating spatial uniform distribution onto electrodes backbone, which played a pivotal role to improve anodic surfaces to host the microorganisms and favor the biofilm formations (as depicted in Figure 1.5.3).

Figure 1.5.3 FESEM images of the fabricated anodes' surface (grey scale), overlapped with a map of the spatial distribution of sulphur (yellow pixels) obtained via EDX (sulphur $K\alpha$ peak at 2.307 keV); and Raman Spectroscopy performed on carbon paper (black curve) and on the surface of a USC PEDOT 200 (blue curve)

These results were reflected and, at the same time, confirmed by the enhancement of electrochemically active area, achieved when the nanostructured and uniform layer of PEDOT:PSS was deposited onto carbon-based material (Figure 1.5.4a and 1.5.4b). Indeed, USC PEDOT showed an electrochemically active area in the range between 15 cm² to 17 cm², which was two times higher than the one proper of carbon-based electrodes. All features of these samples proved to be suitable to improve the anodes electrodes affecting the overall performance of MFCs. Figure 1.5.4c) highlighted a higher voltage output reached when PEDOT:PSS layers were deposited on a carbon backbone. Furthermore, MFCs featuring the PEDOT:PSS layer achieved a maximum potential, respectively, equal to (1.1 ± 0.3) mV (USC PEDOT 50), (1.31 ± 0.06) mV (USC PEDOT 100) and (1.6 ± 0.2) mV (USC PEDOT 200). Such values are almost twice as much as the voltage reached when bare carbon paper was involved as anode electrode, which is equal to (0.9 ± 0.1) mV.

Figure 1.5.4 a) Cyclic voltammograms obtained in hexacyanoferrate electrolyte, at 100 mV·s⁻¹ scan rate, on all investigated electrodes: USC PEDOT 50 (red line), USD PEDOT 100 (blue line), USC PEDOT 200 (green line) and bare carbon paper (black line); b) Determination of electrochemical active surface area, obtained by fitting the peak oxidation currents (i_p) observed in CVs as function of the square root of the scan rate. By inverting Matsuda's equation (Equation 1), these slopes provided the EASA values; c) Average performance computed over each triplet of MFC devices employed during the operative phase. Each black triangle represents one refill event with 1 g/L sodium acetate electrolyte solution.

Devices featuring USC-deposited PEDOT:PSS electrodes showed a three-fold higher Energy recovery with respect to control cells, reaching a maximum value of (13 ± 2) J·m⁻³. Furthermore, the optimal PEDOT:PSS concentration for

the MFCs improvement is in line with the values reported in the literature for other deposition methods. In conclusion, this work demonstrates that USC is a promising technique for application in BES.

Task 1.6 Aqueous phase reforming (POLITO DISAT) Pirone

Biorefinery-derived wastewater is a valuable source of energy and chemicals thanks to its organic loading. However, it is constituted by different compounds which influence the performance of a catalytic valorization process. Hence, it has been investigated treatment procedures to obtain hydrogen via aqueous phase reforming (APR) of a synthetic hydrothermal liquefaction-derived wastewater (HTL-WW). As a case study, attention has been focused on the underlying driving forces for performance differences in the APR of mono- and bi-component solutions of carboxylic acids as a model corn stover HTL-WW over Pt catalysts via a combined experimental and theoretical approach. In mono-component solutions, the conversion ranked as glycolic acid > propionic acid \approx acetic acid, and the same was found for the hydrogen production tendency. Binary solutions of glycolic and acetic acid, with different concentration among the constituents, show a strong inhibition of the acetic acid reactivity due to the prevalent adsorption of glycolic acid on Pt surface. The results from the APR of acetic and propionic acid solutions are less affected by such phenomena. DFT results show that there are strong, attractive lateral interactions between carboxylic acids due to intermolecular hydrogen bonding that cause all carboxylic acids to preferentially adsorb in dimer structures. The lateral interaction strength was determined for both pure and binary mixtures of carboxylic acid dimers, with results showing that pure mixtures of carboxylic acids have stronger attractions and that glycolic acid dimers see the strongest attractions due to the added terminal hydroxyl functional group.

Task 1.7 Materials for Hydrogen production (UNITO, POLITO DISAT Team).

POLITO DISAT Team

The catalyst used for the APR reaction is a 5% Pt/C, provided by a commercial supplier in powder form, of which 80% had a size < 106 μm . The catalyst was used as received. Pt/Al₂O₃ samples prepared by impregnation in DISAT lab has been also tested, for the sake of comparison.

UNITO Team

Materials for Hydrogen Evolution Reaction (HER) were investigated by UNITO. In this context, nanostructured metal oxides show, due to the large surface area to volume ratio, unique chemical and physical properties with applications in electronics, catalysis, sensors, etc. Here, the attention was focused on the intermetallic compound Mo₃Al₈, produced in form of ribbons after arc melting and rapid solidification by melt spinning, that was used as a precursor to obtain nanostructured molybdenum oxides. Single and double-step free corrosion of the melt spun ribbons have been studied in 1 M KOH, 1 M HF and 1.25 M FeCl₃ at room temperature. In both cases, nanostructured molybdenum oxides were obtained on the surface layer showing a thickness of few microns. Electrocatalytic capability for HER of different batches of the produced material was tested in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ showing low onset potential (between -50 mV and -45 mV), small Tafel slopes (between 89 mV dec⁻¹ and 92 mV dec⁻¹) and high exchange current densities (between 0.08 mA cm⁻² and 0.35 mA cm⁻²). The results obtained show that nanostructured oxides for HER can be obtained through a fast, simple, low-cost and sustainable process using cheap and abundant starting materials.

Output and results:

The overall activities that have been performed in this reporting period are the following

Review of standardized protocols and testing infrastructures for testing Proton Exchange Membrane electrolyzers;

In-depth analysis of the specific impact of the MIMIT decree 7/7/2023 regulation on reversible SOEFC systems;

During the third semester of the project, we investigate the performance of all MFCs implemented and developed by applying optimized bio-anodes,

Hydrogen Evolution Reaction (HER) were investigated.

Moreover, investigations on catalyst deactivating phenomena in the efforts of H₂ recovery from wastewaters offer significant insights into the utilization of APR for industrial-like multi-component solutions, as well as for any catalytic

process involving small organic compounds in an aqueous phase.

Deviations (if applicable):

No deviations

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

None

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

For the next reporting period we expect to share results on the behavior of electrocatalysts for H₂ evolution at cathode and their integration in bio-electrolysers and extend the analysis on HER.

1.2.2 Research Module 2

Research Module n. 2:	Start month: M1	End month: M36
Title: Hydrogen storage		
Location in Mezzogiorno: N		
RM Leader	UNITO	
Partners involved	POLITO	
Type of action:	<i>Industrial Research</i>	
Effort in person/months:	UNITO: 0,114	POLITO: 1,41
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):		
<p>Innovative solutions will be developed to produce hybrid materials for the chemical storage of hydrogen. This ambitious goal will be achieved by combining species with a high gravimetric hydrogen content such as ammonia borane or with organic aromatic compounds containing heteroatoms such as nitrogen. Within the project, stable materials with up to one hundred release/regeneration cycles with high hydrogen release capacity will be produced. A technical solution will then be implemented that will couple the materials for storage with a controlled release system by means of thermal stimulation based on their confinement in heat exchanger-based systems.</p>		
Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):		
Task 2.1 Aminoborane materials for hydrogen storage (POLITO DISAT) Pirri		
<p>The project activities has been focused on the production of confined ammoniaborane systems into polymeric matrix. The first approach has been focused on the production of biopolymer derived materials contained an active catalyst layer for the regeneration. The material showed performances beyond the state of the art with remarkably hydrogen gravimetric density and regenerability. Further data will be available after the patent depositing.</p> <p>The second approach enforced was based on the encapsulation on ammonia borane into sulphonated poly (ellagic acid) reaching a 1.2 wt.% pure hydrogen production.</p> <p>The third approach has been focused on direct hydrolysis of ammonia borane using red mud as catalyst in order to valorize a complex wastestream. This research let to the quantitative release of hydrogen in less than 3 min at 40 °C.</p>		
Task 2.2 Aromatic heteroatom compounds materials for hydrogen storage (POLITO DISAT) Pirri		

This task has been focused on the production of high boiling point amine mixture containing ammonia borane in high concentration aiming to modulate its side reactivity. This approach led to the total suppression of borazine production allowing to preserve the boron content of the mixture reaching a 1.9 wt.% pure hydrogen production. Furthermore, the mechanism of side reactivity suppression was investigated also using simulation tool to deeply understand it and rationalize further improvements.

Task 2.3 Development and integration of storage systems based on metal hydrides in mobility systems (UNITO)

The use of hydrogen carriers for mobility systems requires a high gravimetric density. One of the main limitations of the use of metal hydrides as energy carriers is the limited values of it. In order to overcome this issue, the use of High Entropy Alloys has been suggested.

The microstructural, structural and hydrogen sorption properties of four equiatomic refractory high entropy alloys (RHEAs) based on transition elements Ti, V, Cr, Co, Fe, Zr and Ta have been investigated. TiVCrFeTa, TiVCrFeZr, TiVCrCoTa and TiVCrCoZr RHEAs were prepared by arc melting. Structural and microstructural studies were performed by X-ray Diffraction (XRD) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), respectively, whereas hydrogen sorption has been investigated with a Sievert-type apparatus.

Preliminary thermodynamic calculations performed with empirical relations and CALPHAD suggested the presence of a BCC phase, together with C14 and C15 type Laves phase in all RHEAs. In fact, a homogeneous mixture has been revealed by XRD and SEM, with the presence of a matrix of BCC phase, with precipitates of Laves phases.

For some RHEAs an easy hydrogenation was obtained at room temperature and moderate hydrogen pressure (i.e. 30 bar), while in some cases activation was successful only at 300 °C.

PCI curves were measured for these alloys at 21 °C, 100 °C, 200 °C and 300 °C and hydrogen storage properties analysed upon cycling. A maximum hydrogen storage capacity ~ 1.2 and 1.8 wt% was obtained for TiVCrFeZr and TiVCrCoZr, respectively.

Experimental results highlighted the role of Ti-rich Laves compounds in promoting activation, but the occurrence of stable hydrides strongly limited hydrogen storage properties.

Output and results:

- Production of confined ammoniaborane systems into polymeric matrix.
- High boiling point amine mixture containing ammonia borane in high concentration.
- High Entropy Alloys as hydrogen carriers for mobility systems.

Deviations (if applicable):

No deviations

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

None

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

- Simulations on high boiling point amine mixture.
- Patent depositing

1.2.3 Research Module 3

Research Module n. 3:	Start month: M1	End month: M36
Title: Hydrogen distribution and transport		
Location in Mezzogiorno: N		
RM Leader	POLITO	
Partners involved	Envipark	
Type of action:	<i>Industrial Research</i>	

Effort person/months:	in POLITO:	2,63	Envipark:	1,34				
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Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):

The task aims to develop methods and procedures to design and validate infrastructures for hydrogen distribution and transport

Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):

Task 3.1 Techno-economic analysis and system optimization for renewable infrastructure deployment (POLITO DENERG)

The activity done in the first semester of the second year is the application of a MILP-based optimization framework to the cost-optimal design of power-to-hydrogen systems feed by renewable solar electricity for the Italian scenario, and the results have been published in a scientific paper:

Marocco, Paolo, Marta Gandiglio, and Massimo Santarelli. "Optimal design of PV-based grid-connected hydrogen production systems." Journal of Cleaner Production 434 (2024): 140007.

Summary of the research

A cost-optimal design of power-to-hydrogen (PtH) systems is crucial to produce hydrogen at the lowest specific cost. New challenges arise when it comes to ensuring a reliable and cost-effective hydrogen supply in the presence of variable renewable energy sources. In this context, the aim of this analysis is to investigate the optimal design of PV-based grid-connected hydrogen production systems under different scenarios. To this end, an optimisation framework based on the mixed integer linear programming (MILP) technique is developed. Results are presented by employing a set of techno-economic and environmental indicators to provide general guidance on how to optimally size PtH systems, going beyond the analysis of a specific case study.

The analysis is applied to Italy and particular attention is paid to exploring the impact of the price of grid electricity. The results indicate that the price of grid electricity strongly affects the optimal design of PtH systems. Specifically, in scenarios with high electricity prices, it is economically convenient to significantly oversize the PV plant and the electrolyser. The optimal PV ratio, representing the ratio between the PV size and the electrolyser size, increases from 1.6 to 2.7 as the electricity price rises from 50 to 300 €/MWh. Additionally, when electricity prices exceed approximately 120 €/MWh, the optimal electrolyser size (in terms of hydrogen production under rated conditions) becomes almost three times larger than the average hydrogen demand. By comparing grid-connected and off-grid scenarios, the importance of the electrical grid is also highlighted: even when poorly used, it plays a crucial role in limiting the size of the hydrogen storage. The levelised cost of hydrogen for the optimal PtH configuration falls within the range of 3.5–7 €/kg (depending on the price of grid electricity) and increases to 8.2 €/kg when the system operates off-grid. Finally, the hydrogen carbon footprint, quantified as $\text{kg}_{\text{CO}_2, \text{e}}/\text{kg}_{\text{H}_2}$, is also explored. Considering the current price and carbon intensity of grid electricity, the cost-optimal PtH configuration already involves the production of renewable hydrogen ($<3 \text{ kg}_{\text{CO}_2, \text{e}}/\text{kg}_{\text{H}_2}$).

Figure 3.1.2 – a) LCOH as a function of the electricity purchase price (from 50 to 300 €/MWh), and b) LCOH for the 100% PV-based configuration. Two main scenarios are analysed: 1) no remuneration for the excess PV electricity (black-edge circles), and 2) the electricity sale price is set equal to 40% of the electricity purchase price (blue-edge triangles).

Reference

Marocco, Paolo, Marta Gandiglio, and Massimo Santarelli. "Optimal design of PV-based grid-connected hydrogen production systems." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 434 (2024): 140007.

Task 3.2 Test procedures/protocols for leak tests on an innovative heat exchanger for HRS application (ENVIPARK)

The activities are designed to accompany the development of innovative heat exchangers and continued on the basis of the evidence gathered during the first project period. Test protocols were defined to verify the leakage of the exchangers using helium as the test gas under the defined pressure conditions. A test infrastructure was designed and set up and the first equipment validation campaigns were conducted. Activities followed with the consolidation of test protocols and infrastructure and their application on prototype heat exchangers. The company is now analysing the results to define improvements to its product.

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Task 3.3 Hydrogen distribution via natural gas transport and distribution net (POLITO DISAT)

During the recent semester, extensive research has been conducted on the separation of hydrogen from hydrogen-methane mixtures and other gases using intrinsically microporous polymers (IMPs). IMPs, characterized by their rigid and highly porous structures, are ideal for gas separation due to their high surface areas and selective gas permeation properties.

PIMs (Polymers of Intrinsic Microporosity), feature a unique network of interconnected voids that facilitate selective gas permeation. These polymers are engineered to maximize free volume, thereby enhancing their ability to discriminate between gases of different molecular sizes.

A key focus of our research has been on PIM-1, a well-known PIM with a robust framework ideal for gas separation. PIM-1 is synthesized through the polymerization of tetrafluoroterephthalonitrile and spirobisindane, forming a highly rigid and porous structure that is particularly effective for hydrogen separation due to its size-selective microporous network. Our team has developed several functional modifications to the PIM-1 polymer to improve its gas separation efficiency. By optimizing the hydrolysis process, we have successfully prepared a fully hydrolyzed form of PIM-1 in a matter of hours, significantly accelerating our research capabilities. The introduction of carboxylic groups into the PIM-1 structure led to a reduction in microporosity, which, paradoxically, increased selectivity between methane (with

a larger kinetic diameter) and hydrogen (with a smaller kinetic diameter). Further chemical modifications have transformed PIM-1 into a polymer with properties akin to ionic liquids, which help to block and further reduce the micropores, thus enhancing hydrogen selectivity even more. In parallel, we have explored the use of mixed-matrix membranes by incorporating microporous carbons into previous polymeric matrices. This approach aims to verify and increase the selective diffusion of hydrogen through these carbons, potentially improving the efficiency of future membrane productions. The ongoing evaluations of these new materials are promising. As we continue to develop membranes with high permeability and selectivity, our focus remains on addressing the challenges of large-scale production and economic feasibility, controlling physical aging, enhancing mechanical strength with non-porous nanofillers, and improving the flexibility of ceramic membranes. These efforts are crucial for advancing the development of efficient hydrogen/methane separation membranes, and they hold significant potential for industrial applications in energy and environmental sectors.

Output and results:

Application of a MILP-based optimization framework to the cost-optimal design of power-to-hydrogen systems feed by renewable solar electricity for the Italian scenario. A publication was prepared.

Development of innovative heat exchangers.

Deviations (if applicable):

No deviations

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

None

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

Improvement of the prototype heat exchangers.

1.2.4 Research Module 4

Research Module n. 4:	Start month: M1	End month: M36
Title: E-fuels: CO2 recovery and conversion		
Location in Mezzogiorno: N		
RM Leader	POLITO	
Partners involved	UNITO	
Type of action:	<i>Industrial Research</i>	
Effort in person/months:	POLITO: 0,22	UNITO: 0,292
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):		
Research work has been focused on the development of catalysts for hydrogenating CO ₂ to methanol.		
Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):		
Task 4.1		
POLITO DISAT		
The investigation on binary In-Cu oxide co-precipitated materials as candidate catalysts for hydrogenating CO ₂ to methanol has been extended to electrochemical process (after having studied the classical thermochemical one in previous semesters), to evaluate the catalytic performance in the mentioned conversion processes. In-rich binary material exhibits remarkable selectivity (>60%) to methanol along with high activity for CO ₂ conversion (>2%) at 21 bar and 300 °C, achieving a productivity of about 265 mg _{MeOH} h ⁻¹ g _{In} ⁻¹ , which is almost 3 times higher than that of the bare In ₂ O ₃ catalyst. Such a catalyst was demonstrated to be		

active for formate production in the electrochemical process as the main product. Ex situ characterization after testing proved that the In_2O_3 phase was the active site of methanol synthesis during CO_2 hydrogenation at high temperatures and pressures. In contrast, depending on the cell configuration, different indium interfaces were stabilized at the electrocatalyst surface under ambient conditions. It is envisioned that the co-presence of In^0 , In_2O_3 , and $\text{In}(\text{OH})_3$ phases increases the local amount of $^*\text{CO}$ intermediates, promoting the formation of more reduced products, such as ethanol and 2-propanol, through the $^*\text{CO}$ dimerization reaction in the electrochemical process. These findings highlight the potential of nonreducible hydroxides as promoters in the electrochemical CO_2 reduction process.

On the other hand, thermochemical processes have been also investigated to optimize the products than can be obtained in the hydrogenation of CO_2 in order to produce e-fuels. In particular, it has been studied the catalytic conversion of dimethyl ether (obtained via direct hydrogenation of carbon dioxide) into olefins (DTO), tailoring the acidity of ZSM-5 zeolite catalyst via surface passivation.

Four different ZSM-5 samples having different acidity are prepared and tested: two MFI-type zeolites having silicon-to-aluminum ratio equal to 25 and 50 and two additional samples obtained by external passivation of the parent zeolite with a layer of Silicalite-1, leading to a core-shell structure. Each sample has been characterized to assess textural properties, structure, composition, and acidity, and then tested for dimethyl ether (DME) conversion at different reaction temperatures between 300 and 375 °C. The analysis of produced mixture revealed the simultaneous presence of hydrocarbons and methanol. DME conversion grows by increasing the temperature. Propylene is the most abundant hydrocarbon detected during all the time-on-stream analyses. Especially at 375 °C, the investigated samples having greater acidity show faster deactivation due to coking. Samples with lower acidity are thus more stable but, on the other hand, present higher methanol selectivity and lower hydrocarbons yield.

UNITO

The UNITO team works on combining previous results on CO_2 capture materials, with novel reduction functionality leading to synthetic fuels. In particular, two different capture platforms were considered as candidates to host reductive functionalization: Metal Organic Frameworks (MOFs) and MgO loaded zeolites. In the previous reporting period, a series of samples of adsorbers/catalysts based on the UiO-67 MOF framework has been synthesized. In the present reporting period, the materials have been characterized in terms of:

- Crystallinity and phase composition
- Surface area and textural properties
- Surface characterization using FTIR of probe molecules
- Thermal stability.

Concerning the other class of materials under consideration (MgO/Y zeolites), the activity is currently on hold due to technical considerations. In fact. Preliminary models and characterization results have shown that the CO_2 capture performances of these materials are not as promising as it was expected. Therefore, the activity is now focused on the first class of materials (UiO67 MOFS).

Output and results:

UNITO

Characterization data for the materials (phases, cristallinity, texture, Specific Surface area, FTIR (with CO and CO_2 probes), thermal stability). Publication.

POLITO

Results highlight the potential of nonreducible hydroxides as promoters in the electrochemical CO_2 reduction process.

Publications

Deviations (if applicable):

No deviations

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

None

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

Analysis is now focussed on UiO67 MOFS materials.

1.2.5 Research Module

Explain the work carried out in RM5 during the reporting period by providing details of the activities carried out by each beneficiary/affiliated entity involved.

Research Module n. 5:		Start month: M1		End month: M36	
Title: E-fuels: Technologies, components and applications for FC mobility					
Location in Mezzogiorno: Y					
RM Leader	POLITO				
Partners involved	CNR-ITM	ENVIPARK			
Type of action:	Industrial Research				
Effort person/months:	in POLITO:	9,45	CNR-ITM:	Envipark:	1
Objective(s) description (for the reporting period):					
Development of new ionic conductive membranes, analysis of innovative technologies for FC manufacturing, design of high efficiency and low incumbrance and mass air compressors for air supply, design of application of FC to road and water mobility, design of novel mechanical bearings for high speed rotors to avoid air compressors in FC-based mobile applications.					
Summary of the activities envisaged for the period detailing the contribution by each Partner/Research Team for each objective (provide measurable indicators, if available):					
Summary of the activities envisaged					
Task 5.1 New strategies for ionic conductive membranes (CNR-ITM)					
5.1.1. Summary					
In the previous reporting period have been selected, by a combined theoretical and experimental approach, two green (bio-based) solvents indicated as #13 and #14 for the preparation of polymer electrolyte membranes (PEMs).					
In this reporting period the protocol for the preparation of the Nafion PEMs was optimized by a thermal and chemical post treatment. The membranes produced were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIC), zeta potential measurements, chemical stability in oxidative conditions (Fenton's test), ion exchange capacity, swelling and mechanical test. The same tests were carried out with a commercial sample of Nafion 212 (DuPont) used as benchmark. A first generation of mixed matrix membranes were also prepared using graphene oxide (GO) as functional additive					
5.1.1.1 Output and results:					
The membrane preparation protocol includes the following steps: dispersion of the Nafion in the selected solvent, casting, solvent evaporation under controlled temperature and humidity and post treatment of the membrane (thermal and chemical treatment). The membranes produced using solvents #13 and #14 were characterized by a dense structure (Fig. 5.1.2.1). They were completely transparent and flexible.					

Figure 5.1.1.1. SEM images of the commercial Nafion 212 (DuPont) (a), the Nafion membranes prepared with the green solvents #13 (b) and #14 (c) (1000X and 5000X magnification)

Stress-strain elongation test showed excellent properties of the prepared Nafion membranes (breaking modulus > 7 MPa; elongation at break > 70%). They exhibited also excellent oxidative stability: after prolonged contact with an oxidative environment (2 ppm FeSO_4 3% H_2O_2 ; 80 °C; 3 days) was measured a weight loss of less than 2%.

The membranes were tested by EIS using to determinate the in-plane ionic conductivity at different temperatures. The ionic conductivity of all the samples increased with the temperature in the range 25-70°C (Fig. 5.1.2.2). Nafion membrane prepared with the green solvents #14 had a conductivity similar to the Nafion 212 (DuPont). This result is very interesting considering that the Nafion 212 is one of the most performing commercial membrane. This Nafion 212 is a new generation of DuPont's Nafion membrane prepared by solution casting technique; the previous generation of Nafion membranes like Nafion 115 and Nafion 117 were produced by extrusion cast [<https://www.nafion.com/en/products/sulfonic-membranes>]. No information are available about the type of solvent used in the DuPont's industrial protocol but in most of the research works reported in literature substances of very high concern (SVHC) are used as solvent like N,N-dimethylacetamide [C.-H. Ma et al. Journal of Power Sources 117 (2003) 14–21]. The innovative protocol here developed uses green biobased solvents to produce Nafion membrane.

Figure 5.1.2.2. In-plane conductivity as function of the temperature of the commercial Nafion 212 membrane and the membranes prepared with the green solvents #13 and #14.

Using the solvent #14 a first generation of mixed matrix membrane was prepared adding 1wt% of GO with respect Nafion. It was very important to sonicate the dispersion to achieve a good dispersion of the additive in the formed membrane. The polymeric

membrane was completely transparent (Fig. 5.1.2.3a), while the mixed matrix membrane was characterized by a homogenous black colour due to presence of the GO (Fig 5.1.2.3b). Also, the mixed matrix membrane prepared with the green solvent #14 has a dense structure (Fig 5.1.2.3c-d)

Figure 5.1.1.3. Photo of the polymeric Nafion#14 (a) and mixed matrix Nafion+GO#14 (b) membranes. SEM images of the surface (c) and cross section (d) of the mixed matrix membrane.

The presence of the GO increased the isoelectric point of the mixed matrix membrane with respect the polymeric membrane (4.38 vs 3.44, respectively) because of the presence of acid groups on the GO. Further characterizations of the mixed matrix membrane are in progress.

Main conclusions:

- The preparation protocol of the solution cast polymeric Nafion membranes was optimization by thermal and chemical treatment
- The green solvent #14 was able to give membranes with conductivities similar to the benchmark Nafion212 (DuPont)
- A first generation of mixed matrix membrane containing GO was prepared.

5.1.1.2 Objectives for the next reporting period:

- To complete the characterization of the first generation of Nafion+GO#14 mixed matrix membrane
- Optimization of the mixed matrix membranes protocol, including evaluation of different functional additives

5.1.2 Synthesis of microporous polymer based on benzimidazole groups fluorine-free for proton exchange membrane fuel cells (POLITO DISAT)

Recent studies have focused on Polymer of intrinsically microporosity (PIMs) for their potential in energy applications. The unique porosity of these materials makes them suitable for high-performance gas separation, energy storage, and conversion applications. PIM-1, a polymer well-suited for gas separation due to its intrinsic microporosity, has been the subject of extensive modification to improve its functional properties. Recent experimental activities have included the hydrolysis of cyano groups to carboxylic groups to form C-PIM, utilizing a monomodal microwave reactor under high-temperature and high-pressure conditions. This process resulted in nearly complete hydrolysis, contradicting previous literature findings and demonstrating improved functionality as evidenced by infrared spectroscopy analyses.

Further advancements have involved the incorporation of ionizable groups into PIM-1, leading to the development of SPIM (sulfonated PIM-1). This modification aims to enhance the polymer's ion-exchange capabilities, crucial for applications like proton-exchange membranes in fuel cells. The conductivity tests conducted on SPIM membranes have shown promising results, indicating significant potential for energy-related applications.

At the moment several potential syntheses for various derivatives of PIM-1, including experiments on benzimidazole formation from carboxylic groups and the solubility of BiPIM derivatives were prepared. The scope is to achieve reproducibility and optimization of reaction conditions with a focus on improving the mechanical and chemical stability of the membranes.

Further experiments with SPIM involved permeation tests with graphene to explore its utility in enhancing the selectivity and efficiency of gas separation processes. The success of SPIM in these tests opens new avenues for the development of more robust and efficient energy systems.

The ongoing research into the modifications and applications of PIM-1 underscores its potential in transforming energy applications. With continued focus on enhancing the functionality and stability of these polymers, particularly through sulfonation and other chemical modifications, PIM-1 derivatives are poised to play a significant role in the development of sustainable energy technologies.

5.1.3 MEA fabrication and electrochemical characterization for fuel cells application (POLITO DISAT)

As reported in our previous report, related to the experimental activities performed during the second semester of the project, we investigated catalyst layers deposited onto carbon paper, towards the employment of Ultrasonic Spray Coating (USC) process with the main aim to create a uniform distributed catalyst layer onto carbon paper, properly modified with a microporous layer (MPL-CP). We used the same ink proposed in previous report, composed of catalyst powders (10wt% of Pt onto carbon, purchased from Sigma Aldrich), ionomer solution (5wt% of Nafion in water) and solvents isopropanol and deionized water (IPA: DI) with a volume ratio of 3:4. To demonstrate the effectiveness of USC process to optimized the 3-phase-boundary, leading thus to obtain good performance of deposited catalyst layers towards the Oxygen Reduction Reaction (ORR), we investigated and compared two different amounts of Pt/C, respectively equal to 0.1 mg cm^{-2} and 0.075 mg cm^{-2} , which turned out to be much lower than the quantitative commonly used to make a catalytic layer for H-Fuel cells, which is 0.5 mg cm^{-2} . The size of ink droplets landing on the polymer electrolyte membrane was controlled using ultrasonic nozzles at the frequencies of 90 kHz, while, on the contrary, a substrate temperature of 80°C was imposed. This temperature affected the solvent evaporation, that consequently influences the pores distribution. The larger are the pores, the lower is cathode-flooding, leading thus to enhance mass transport of oxygen. Furthermore, this research activity has led to design a gas diffusion electrodes (GDEs) composed by carbon paper acts as carbon backbone, suitable to ensure good electrical conductivity, modified with a microporous layer, on which catalyst layers, based on 0.075 mg cm^{-2} and 0.1 mg cm^{-2} , was directly deposited. GDE setup was employed to test these catalyst layers by mimicking the same conditions typical of realistic Proton Exchange membrane, such as acidic pH environment, relevant applied current densities and potentials. With the main aim of getting as close as possible to MEA conditions, the Nafion 117 membrane was applied in close contact with GDE electrode thus manufactured, during characterization. Figure 5.1.3.1 reports and compares the obtained results, confirming the effectiveness of USC process as the method to deposit catalyst layers onto carbon-based materials, since best performance can be obtained also with the lower amount pf Pt/C, close to 0.075 mg cm^{-2} .

Figure 5.1.3.1 Polarization curves that have a key role in determining the ORR performance of analyzed GDEs.

Moreover, the research activity, during this third semester, also made it possible to start developing an MEA composed of a carbonaceous LIG material, obtained from CO₂ laser writing directly on the Kapton membrane, suitable to design a new carbon-electrode. We demonstrate the capability to ensure the design of LIG membrane, starting from Kapton, leading thus to obtain a final carbon electrode with a good electrical characterization not only along the plane but also along the membrane thickness, as represented in Figure 5.1.3.1. all results allowed us to submit a patent about this new experimental approach. During the next experimental steps, we test these new LIG-Based electrodes with Pt/C deposited as catalyst layer.

Task 5.2 Innovative technologies for FC manufacturing and analysis of automation processes in stack packaging and production (ENVIPARK; POLITO DISAT)

5.2.1 Analysis of innovative plasma-based technologies for FC manufacturing (ENVIPARK)

The semester's activities have been focused on the initiation of the state-of-the-art analysis related to the use of plasma technologies in the manufacturing of electrochemical conversion devices employing hydrogen (fuel cell and electrolyzers). The activity saw interaction with some international technology providers to gain information on the latest developments in terms of processes and enabling technologies.

In particular, the processes examined mainly involved treatments designed to improve the adhesion of components of different materials (surface cleaning, activation and deposition); in addition, there has been a rise in sealing treatments intended for anti-corrosion coating. These preliminary tasks have therefore been laid for the next activities which will also have an experimental dimension geared toward testing new deposition technologies with the aim of eliminating solvent-based primers and adhesives from processes.

Following the initial phase of exploring the possible solutions in terms of creating coatings with dual adhesive and anti-corrosion functionality, deposition tests were carried out using various industrially sustainable solutions. For this purpose, preliminary steel samples are being produced which will be subjected to tests and characterizations. The technology used is Plasmamatreat deposition technology (Plasma Plus), a solution that allows integration into various types

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of movement systems. A program of in-depth workshops lasting a working week had been defined which aims to exchange experiences and skills on the topics covered by the study with the participation of technology providers.

The activity of the workshop held in the Italian headquarters of Plasmatrete GmbH, at Vega Park in Marghera (VE), saw the creation of a program aimed to carry out a series of tests intended both at consolidating the processes already inserted in the industrial context in the plants sited in Germany, and to test new prototypes which should allow an improvement in terms of process effectiveness and efficiency in processing times.

A brief look at the battery manufacturing process as a model

Step 1 Slurry preparation

Active material, binder and conductive agent are mixed in specific mass ratios.

Step 2 Coating & drying

By a tape casting procedure, the electrode slurry is coated on the current collectors.

Step 3 Calendering

During calendering the porous electrodes are compressed by driving them through two cylinders.

Step 4 Cutting electrodes

The electrodes are cut or punched into strips of a desired shape.

Step 5 Cell assembly

The electrodes are bound or stacked together with the separator.

Step 6 Electrolyte filling & formation

Electrolyte is injected: it is important that the electrolyte fully permeates and fills the pores

While the first 5 steps typically are a matter of minutes each, complete filling can take up to several hours, making this rate determining step of the whole process

In the first phase of our workshop, we therefore focused on the possibilities offered by plasma technologies (Plasmatrete GmbH) to improve this part of the process.

Some preliminary industrial opinions collected stated that:

- a) Problems for wetting of electrode material increase very much when electrode thickness is increased. There, complete filling can take long (hours, days) and is really a pain point. Filling can be checked with electrochemical measurements and from this indirectly the wetting completeness can be deduced, but a direct method to measure and to improve would be so helpful.
- b) Our focus right now is on reduction of the filling time of cells with electrolyte. Currently, a generous time frame is used to assure proper filling. We want to reduce this by good wetting control and strategy, rather than guesswork and overcome this bottleneck in battery cell production.

Technical considerations

Performance:

Electrode wetting is crucial for optimum electrochemical performance of cell and directly affects e.g. capacity retention and cell lifetime at the high charge/discharge rates. Scaling from coin cells to industrial pouch cells, wetting sets the limit for energy and power density

Safety:

Incomplete wetting brings the danger of dendrite formation, posing a big risk for the safety of the battery

Costs:

Reducing the waiting period can save precious process time, increasing production capacity

Sheng, Yangming, "Investigation of Electrolyte Wetting in Lithium Ion Batteries: Effects of Electrode Pore Structures and Solution" (2015). Theses and Dissertations. 1080.

Scientific considerations

Incomplete wetting creates barriers for ion transport

Incomplete wetting basically means you're not using all active material that you have in your cell

Ion transfer is limited, limiting your electrochemical performance

Plasma applications in the different processing phases

Openair-Plasma® in EV Battery

plasmatreat
KRÜSS

Activation prior to cell-to-cell bonding

Anti Corrosion barrier coating to a sealing system

Increase the wetting behavior of coated electrodes

Surface cleaning prior to
1. Gap filler
2. Structural bonding

Increase the wetting behavior of the current collector

Cleaning of battery tabs

Cleaning prior to wire bonding

Activation prior to cell-to-cell bonding

Step 1 - Increase the surface tension of the metal foils

Openair-Plasma significantly increase the surface tension of metal foils

- a) Anode copper foil or
- b) Cathode aluminium foil

Surface tension and wettability are important topics. Especially when it comes to the adhesion of the active material

The Openair-Plasma treatment offer a high speed in line cleaning with full process control up to 100m/min and in some case more. In the replication of the tests, we tried different process speeds (corresponding to different exposure times of the surface to be treated to the plasma) going from 25m/min up to 100m/min.

Step 2 – Increase the wetting behaviour of coated foils

In the second phase, Openair Plasma technology was used to treat the surface of the active material in order to reduce the electrolyte filling time

The results show that the electrolyte filling can be significantly accelerate by using Openair-Plasma

Without Treatment after 3sec

With Openair-Plasma® Treatment after 3 sec

	Untreated	Openair-Plasma®
Cathode	2 min	3 s

A more useful evaluation of the material properties before and after the plasma treatment was possible thanks to the use of the tensiometer.

Introducing the wetting rate K, a tensiometer can be used to measure:

- 1) How quick the wetting process occurs (wetting rate);
- 2) How much liquid is adsorbed in total (completeness)

The Washburn theory describes the sorption of liquids into capillaries

Sample (n=15)	Wetting Rate K [mm/s ^{0.5}]	Std. Deviation [mm/s ^{0.5}]	Average R ²
Cathode	0.175	0.014 (8.0%)	0.992
Anode	0.244	0.017 (7.0%)	0.997

Using this analytical methodology, it was seen how slurry composition affect wetting rate.

It is also possible to learn what degree of calendaring gives the best results

Finally, thanks to this analytical methodology, it was possible to study how the use of plasma allows the complete wettability of the electrode

Different combinations of process parameters were used in order to achieve a significant increase in the performance of the material without introducing unwanted effects.

Some of the conditions tested are shown below

Before Plasma activation

Sample	Wetting Rate [mg/s ^{0.5}]
Anode (Graphite)	0.23 ± 0.05

After Plasma activation

Sample	Wetting Rate [mg/s ^{0.5}]
Anode (Graphite)	0.23 ± 0.05
Anode + Plasma	0.46 ± 0.11

Step 3 – Activation prior to cell-to-cell bonding

Cell-to-cell bonding can be realized with a) pressure-sensitive adhesive layer or by using a liquid adhesive (e.g. Polyurethane). During the tests carried out, it has been verified that the plasma system used allows the components to be treated without a significant increase in temperature.

The analysis confirms that stronger bonds are generated to avoid any damage due to vibration effects or thermal expansion of the cells
During the workshop we replicated the best conditions previously studied.

Surface Energy shows a good correlation to direct adhesion testing. But unlike the latter, it is non-destructive, much quicker and doesn't need a lab

Conclusions

We can say that the study of this type of process, which uses an atmospheric pressure plasma that can be perfectly integrated into automotive platforms, is able to guarantee a series of advantages which we list below:

Plasma technology (Openair-Plasma®) increases the surface tension and wettability of material.

Using plasma, no additional mechanical or chemical surface preparation necessary.

This type of treatment is fully automatable, process-reliable pretreatment (PCU).

The process with plasma is environmentally friendly.

Increase the process reliability.

5.2.2 Laser-based processing of nanostructured carbon electrodes for FC (POLITO DISAT)

As anticipated in the first and in the second progress reports and since the preparation of graphene-based materials (LIG) of polymers received great success thanks to the combination of simplicity with high speed, during all research activities of third semester, we employed CO₂ laser writing to transform polymers, in bulk or in nanostructured arrangement, into Laser Induced Graphene (LIG). Moreover, starting from all results achieved during the research activities of second semester that allowed demonstrating an intrinsic ORR activity of the LIG-S samples, confirmed by a number of electrons of 3.75, which is close to the ideal four-electron number obtained with platinum catalysts, during the third progress review, we investigate the effect of co-catalysis towards Oxygen Reduction Reaction, by decorating/modifying LIG-S surfaces with LIG-NFs. During the research activities of this third semester, we want to demonstrate how the simultaneous presence of nitrogen defects, due to the presence of LIG-NFS, combined with the sulfonated defects proper of LIG-S, resulted to be pivotal to improve the electrocatalytic properties of final samples towards Oxygen Reduction Reaction (ORR). To this purpose, the investigation of phasic-chemical features of LIG-and their morphological properties turns out to be necessary. Moreover, as anticipated in the first progress report completed in May 2023, we can produce and design carbon-based materials in the form of nanostructured and bulk materials. The carbonization of the starting polymeric material is induced by CO₂-laser writing and achieved in an ambient atmosphere due to the alkaline treatment to which the starting polymeric material is subjected, based on a patent. The nanostructured polymeric material was obtained by implementing electrospinning process and starting from a polymeric solution of Polyacrylonitrile (PAN), which showed a high yield of carbonization, dissolved in N-N DMF. As spun nanofibers were properly treated in an alkaline environment to ensure the possibility to convert polymeric nanofibers into LIG-NFs by CO₂ laser writing under ambient conditions. PAN nanofibers mats after their exposition at alkaline environment were placed onto sulfonated polyether ether ketone (SPEEK) membrane and subsequently for both two materials, PAN nanofibers and SPEEK film, the photothermal process was initiated by the CO₂ laser scribe, leading thus to ensure complete conversion of both SPEEK film into LIG-S and PAN-NF into LIG-NFs. We demonstrate the preservation of nanostructured material also after its exposition to CO₂ laser writing as reported in Figure 5.2.2.1.a)

and to confirm that LIG-NFs were mostly composed of carbon, as described by Raman Spectrum represented in Figure 5.2.2.1.b). Indeed, Raman spectrum highlighted the presence of D-Peak at $\sim 1350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and G-peak at 1580 cm^{-1} . D-peak is strictly correlated with the presence of defects into carbon lattice, while, on the contrary the G-peak results to be the fingerprint of sp^2 carbon lattices. The ratio between the integrated intensities of D (ID) and G peaks (IG) is an indicator of the crystallinity of the sample. In this case, ID/IG is close to 1, leading thus to define that LIG-NFs was highly crystallized material.

Figure 5.2.2.1 a) SEM images to confirm the preservation of nanostructure also after the CO_2 laser writing; b) Raman Spectra confirmed the carbon-based material obtained after the CO_2 Laser writing suitable to design LIG NFs.

The presence of defects into carbon lattice, underlined by this evident D-peak in Raman Spectrum, was confirmed by XPS spectroscopy, implemented to demonstrate the presence inside the LIG-NFs of nitrogen defects, which, as deeply confirmed in the literature, played a pivotal role to improve the electrocatalytic behaviour of LIG-NFs towards Oxygen Reduction Reaction (ORR). In order to assess the presence of the nitrogen defect and their position with respect to the carbon atoms, bound to them, thus establishing whether the nitrogen defect turns out to be graphitic, pyrrolic and/or pyridinic, XPS characterization was implemented, as shown in Figure 5.2.2.2. Indeed, the high-resolution $\text{N}1\text{s}$ spectrum allows us to define the 4 different nitrogen defect species: 1) pyridine nitrogen-N (398.2 eV); 2) pyrrolic-N (399.5 eV); 3) graphitic-central-N (400.9 eV); and 4) graphitic-valley N (403.2 eV). It was possible to determine a high graphitic nitrogen defect content combined with the presence of a significant amount of pyridine nitrogen, corresponding to an atomic percentage of $55.1 \text{ at}\%$ and $26.7 \text{ at}\%$, respectively. This experimental result made it possible to confirm the good catalytic properties of the PAN-NFs material obtained by CO_2 laser writing, together with the excellent electrical properties, the presence of graphitic nuclei as confirmed by RAMAN spectroscopy and the high porosity induced and maintained after laser treatment.

Figure 5.2.2.2. High resolution $\text{N}1\text{s}$ spectra obtained for LIG-NFs, designed by implementing Co_2 laser writing directly onto PAN nanofibers. The presence of Nitrogen defects, proper of LIG-NFs, combined with the Sulfur defects, self-induced into LIG-S materials, allowed improving and optimizing the electrocatalytic properties of final nanostructured catalyst layers, composed by LIG-catalyst layers obtained from polymeric PAN nanofibers using SPEEK as binder.

The presence of Nanofibers ensured their intrinsic properties, such as high continuous porosity and surface area to volume ratio, that are suitable to improve triple phase boundaries, defined as that place where the re-combination among protons, electrons and Oxygen occurred, as represented in Figure 5.2.2.3 To this purpose Figure 5.2.2.3.a) highlight the continuous morphological features of LIG-S, obtained from SPEEK materials; while, on the contrary, by analyzing Figure 5.2.2.3.b) it is possible to appreciate a hierarchical porosity induced in final LIG-nanostructured materials obtained by LIG-NFs and LIG-S.

Figure 5.2.2.3. a) SEM images related to LIG-S were reported to underline a continuous and bulk samples obtained also after the CO₂ laser writing; b) morphological properties of final LIG-nanostructured catalyst layers, made of LIG-NFs and LIG-S, were depicted, leading thus to confirm a high porosity induced thanks to presence of nanofibers.

For this reason, the higher is the TPIs, the better the electro-catalytic properties of catalyst layer toward ORR.

This hypothesis is confirmed by RRDE measurements and GDE characterizations (Figure 5.2.2.4.a) and b)). Figure 5.2.2.4.a) confirmed that LIG NFs onto SPEEK, act as binder, ensures a higher number of electrons, close to 3.91, as close as possible to 4, ensured by Pt considered as the ideal catalyst layer for ORR. Furthermore, improved electro-catalytic properties were confirmed by GDE characterizations. Indeed, from Figure 5.2.2.4. b), it is possible to appreciate from the graph on the bottom part of the slides, how the offset potential for LIG NFs is close to 0.4V, representing the potential at which ORR occurred, is higher than the one reached with LIG from SPEEK (equal to 0.1V).

Figure 5.2.2.4. a) RRDE measurements performed on two different LIG-catalyst layers: the first one is composed by LIG-NFs combined with LIG-S, acting as a binder, that ensure a number of electrons (straight blue line), close to the ideal value of 4, higher than the one achieved with only LIG-S (dot blue line) ; b) polarization curves that have a key role in determining the ORR performance of analyzed GDEs.

5.2.3 Electrohydrodynamic methods for catalysts deposition (POLITO DISAT)

All research activities conducted during this project's phase were focused on the optimization of composition of Pt-based inks, as deeply discussed in the previous report. Independent on the amount of Pt/C dissolved, concentration of Nafion as polymeric-binder, all experimental trials fails, leading thus to conclude that electro-spray is not the suitable process to employ an uniform distribution of nanodrops on the substrate surface. With the purpose to reach the goal of this task,

To achieve the goal of this task, i.e. to employ electrohydrodynamic processes capable of ensuring uniform deposition of the catalytic layer, we synthesized PAN nanofibers by means of the electrospinning process. Furthermore, to make the polymer

nanofibre mat suitable for use as a catalytic layer, CO₂ laser writing was implemented to obtain LIG nanofibers (LIG NFs). The experimental process followed/implemented to transform the PAN nanofibers into LIG NFs was deeply described in the previous Task 5.2.2. The preservation of nanostructuring of LIG-NFs was demonstrated, allowing to reach a final catalyst layer able to couple the intrinsic properties of nanofibers, such as high surface area, large continuous porosity, with the presence of self-induced nitrogen defects suitable to improve electrocatalytic behavior of final sample. It is important to consider how the continuous porosity of final LIG NFs played a pivotal role to improve the number and distribution of Triple Phase Interfaces, which is defined as the place where protons, electrons and oxygen molecules interact one with each other, favoring the direct oxygen reduction reaction. Therefore, the continuous porosity improved the diffusion of gases, i.e. oxygen, and protons, which are able to reach the different active catalytic sites within the LIG-NFs.

Preliminary results, conducted by implementing Rotating Ring Disk Electrode measurements, confirmed these hypotheses. All measurements were conducted in alkaline O₂-saturated media, based on 0.1M KOH dissolved in deionized water.

In Figure 5.2.3.1, all results obtained for analyzed materials, are reported. In particular, it is possible to notice that for both LIG-NFs and Pt/C layer, the ring currents (Figure 5.2.3.1.b) are very low with respect to disk currents (Figure 5.2.3.1.a). In line with these results, for both samples the 4-reduction pathway is favored and, as a consequence, the ring current is low. By analyzing the electro-catalytic properties of N-CNFs, compared to those of the Pt/C layer, it is possible to notice that N-CNFs provide an electron transfer close to 3.9, as shown in Figure 5.2.3.1.c, close to the ideal value of 4. Moreover, the percentage of peroxide species for N-CNFs is lower than 25%

Figure 5.2.3.1 a) Disk current and b) Ring current obtained from the RRDE measurements, conducted on LIG-NFs and Pt/C reference samples. c) electron transfer number and H₂O₂-% established by RRDE characterizations of LIG NFs (blue and purple line) compared with the commercial catalyst based on Pt/C (black line).

Future research activities will be focused on the possibility to test the electrocatalytic behavior of LIG NFs also in acidic media, that mimic the typical environment of PEM Fuel Cells, starting from the results described into the Task 5.2.2. Those results, indeed, allowed confirming the good electrocatalytic features of LIG NFs coupled with LIG-S, obtained starting from SPEEK layers, involved as binder for LIG-NFs

5.2.4 Microwave Synthesis of Pt-free catalysts for PEMFCs (POLITO DISAT)

Combining conventional hydrothermal/solvothermal synthesis with microwave-assisted methods indeed offers a promising approach in nanomaterial synthesis, particularly for electrocatalysts. This hybrid approach capitalizes on the strengths of both methods while mitigating their limitations.

In conventional hydrothermal/solvothermal synthesis, the closed reaction system allows for high temperature and pressure conditions, facilitating the growth of high-quality nanostructures. However, the extended reaction durations can be a drawback in terms of both time and energy efficiency. On the other hand, microwave-assisted synthesis offers rapid heating and energy savings, but is typically limited by the boiling point of solvents and lower pressure conditions. This can affect the quality and control of nanostructures produced.

By integrating microwave irradiation into the conventional synthesis process, the hybrid method addresses these limitations. The rapid and volumetric heating provided by microwaves significantly reduces the overall reaction time, from hours to minutes or even seconds. Moreover, the combination of high temperature and pressure achieved through this method promotes the growth of well-defined nanostructures with controlled sizes, shapes, and chemical properties. Hence, this hybrid approach offers a cost-effective, energy-efficient, and scalable method for producing high-performance nanostructured electrocatalysts.

Several reputable companies offer furnaces suitable for microwave-assisted hydrothermal/solvothermal synthesis, including Milestone, CEM, Biotage, MARS, and Anton Paar, and so on. Our laboratory is equipped with both low TRL (Technology Readiness Level) and high TRL microwave reactors from Milestone, enabling the production of electrocatalysts across a wide range of scales from milligrams to grams. The low TRL reactor has a total volume of 100 ml and is capable of reaching high temperatures and pressures up to 260 °C and 50 bars, respectively. The high TRL reactor offers an increased volume of 990 ml and can achieve even higher temperatures, reaching up to 300°C, along with pressures of up to 199 bars. This comprehensive setup allows us to tailor our synthesis process according to the specific requirements of our research, whether we're working on a small-scale exploration or a larger-scale production.

POLITO is leading the charge in developing Pt-free ORR catalysts for PEMFCs application, utilizing microwave-assisted hydrothermal/solvothermal synthesis technique. Our research focuses on two distinct materials:

- 1) Heteroatoms-doped laser-induced graphene (LIG) materials: Here, we utilize the microwave-assisted hydrothermal method to precisely decorate heteroatom active sites within the LIG framework.
- 2) Mesoporous Fe-N-C catalysts: In this second line of investigation, we utilize a microwave-assisted hydrothermal approach to precisely adjust the pore structure of silica, serving as the sacrificial template for Fe-N-C synthesis. Through this method, we finely tune the porosity of the silica template, resulting in mesoporous Fe-N-C catalysts with an optimized pore architecture. This optimization enhances the accessibility of Fe-N active sites and promotes efficient mass diffusion within the gas diffusion electrode. By tailoring the pore structure in this manner, we aim to maximize the catalytic performance of the Fe-N-C catalysts, ultimately enhancing their efficacy in fuel cell applications.

By employing the microwave-assisted synthesis techniques, we aim to tailor the properties of these materials with precision, ultimately advancing the development of efficient and cost-effective Pt-free catalysts for fuel cell applications.

Task 5.3 Test procedures/protocols for FC and components (ENVIPARK; POLITO-DISAT)

5.3.1 (ENVIPARK)

5.3.2 (POLITO-DISAT)

During the third semester of the project, we started to work with the Scribner Associates' Model 850e Fuel Cell Test Station to perform the characterization of single Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells (PEM-FC). The Scribner Associates' Model 850e Fuel Cell Test Station, as represented in Figure 5.3.2.1, is a fully integrated test stand for single cell or short stack testing. It includes two stainless steel humidifiers and two mass flow controllers, three temperature controllers, and an electronic load with built-in current interrupt.

Figure 5.3.2.1. Picture of Scribner Model 850e installed in our lab to perform the characterization of single o stacks of PEM-FCs. The purchased Model 850e includes manual or automatic backpressure, the Model 880 Frequency Response Analyzer for high frequency resistance (HFR) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements, the integrated Model 885 Fuel Cell Potentiostat for linear sweep voltammetry (LSV), cyclic voltammetry (CV) and electrode durability testing, and a humidifier by-pass for wet-dry cycling.

The Model 850e is suitable for use with hydrogen proton exchange membrane (PEM) fuel cells, direct methanol fuel cells (DMFC) and other cell types.

Fuel Cell Store's PEM Fuel Cell Hardware includes all the key components to make such devices operate, given the correct kind of membrane electrode assembly (MEA, Figure 5.3.2.2). It also performs compression of the MEA while providing uniform gas distribution and uniform temperature to the cell. A gold-plated plate serves as current collector plate for the fuel cell. The gold plating provides corrosion protection and good electrical contact with the graphite separator plate. A high purity graphite plate with high electrical conductivity (900 S cm^{-1}) and high thermal conductivity ($117 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) is designed with serpentine gas flow channels and manifold. Two silicone gaskets are included to provide a secure seal for the MEA. High power silicon rubber heaters are installed at both ends of the fuel cell to maintain a constant cell temperature.

Figure 5.3.2.2. Fuel Cell Store's 5-Layer MEAs with integrated gas diffusion layers (GDLs) for use in hydrogen/air fuel cells have been purchased for the PEM Fuel Cell Hardware. Catalyst layers was made of 0.5 mg/cm², 60% platinum on Vulcan on both the anode and the cathode, a 50.8- μ m perfluoro sulfonic acid (PFSA) proton exchange membrane, and 410- μ m thick woven carbon cloth GDLs.

Several Fuel Cell Store's 5-Layer MEAs with integrated gas diffusion layers (GDLs) for use in hydrogen/air fuel cells have been purchased for the PEM Fuel Cell Hardware. They feature a mid-range platinum loading (0.5 mg/cm², 60% platinum on Vulcan) on both the anode and the cathode, a 50.8- μ m perfluoro sulfonic acid (PFSA) proton exchange membrane, and 410- μ m thick woven carbon cloth GDLs. The active area and membrane area are 2.2 x 2.2 cm² and 10 x 10 cm², respectively, and they are compatible with Fuel Cell Store's PEM Fuel Cell Hardware.

Task 5.4 Fuel cells stack modeling and BoP design (POLITO-DENERG; ENVIPARK)

The activity done in the first semester of the second year is the development of a PEMFC stack and system model for an aircraft application. The results of the research have been published in a scientific paper [1].

Summary of the research

The design of a proton-exchange membrane fuel cell system (PEMFC) with the inclusion of liquid hydrogen storage has been carried out. Specifically, a general mathematical model has been developed, which involves multiple scales, ranging from individual cells to aircraft scale.

First, the fuel cell electrochemical model has been developed. The electrochemical analysis of the single cell is based on a PEMFC model developed by Andrei Kulikovskiy [2]. The model allows for obtaining a simplified but accurate analytical solution by incorporating the most relevant processes occurring within the cell. The electrochemical model of the single cell consists of a set of equations that simulate the most relevant transport phenomena occurring within the fuel cell. This model provides results in terms of polarization curve, as well as power and efficiency curves. Additionally, it enables the calculation of reactant flow rates and thermal power to be removed, which are fundamental input for the sizing of the BoP. The polarization curve was calibrated using experimental data extracted from literature. The following figure shows the polarization curve of a PEMFC with good performance from [3] (TEC36VA32 at the beginning of the lifetime, 100 % RH, 150 kPa, 80 °C and 0.1 mgPt/cm²), which has been used for the calibration of the model.

The fuel cell system is composed by the electrochemical stack surrounded by a series of components that constitute its BoP and play a crucial role in managing the stack itself. The following figure illustrates the control volume, regarded as the repetitive unit for the sizing of the fuel cell system, consisting of the stack and the most impactful components of its BoP.

The stack was designed by considering the performance of the single cell and defining its area and the number of cells from a reference stack [4]. From the stack features, it was possible to determine all the input/output quantities referred to the stack: voltage, current, electrical and thermal power, reactant flow rates.

The main energy-demanding components of the BoP were identified and sized in relation to their power requirements. Indeed, these components are powered directly by the fuel cell, underscoring the significance of accurately sizing them to determine the gross power output needed from the stack, as well as the resulting stack size. The power absorbed by the auxiliary units is divided into two different contributions:

- the compressor absorbs a large variable amount of power;
- others: absorb a small, fixed amount of power.

The designed cooling system consists of a closed circuit where a liquid coolant is used to cool the stack and then returns to its initial temperature conditions through an air radiator.

The successive step was to model the propulsion system of the full hydrogen-powered aircraft. This model identifies three different main sections: the hydrogen tank, the fuel cell system (including stacks and BoP) and the electric motor. The commercial regional aircraft ATR72-600 [5], whose specifics are summarized in the following figure, was selected for the sizing of the propulsion system.

ATR72-600 aircraft		
Main features		
Standard configuration	72 seats	
Engines Pratt & Whitney Canada	PW127 M/N	
Take-off power (half-wing)	1846	kW
Max cruise power (half-wing)	1590	kW
Weights		
Max take-off weight (MTOW)	22,800	kg
Structure	10,479	kg
Max payload	7550	kg
Propellers	342	kg
Kerosene-based propulsion system (2x engines + fuel + fuel system)	4429	kg
En-route performance		
Max altitude	15,000	ft
	(4600)	(m)

Figure 5.4.3 – Technical data of ATR72-600

As indicated in the figure, the maximum take-off weight (MTOW) of the selected aircraft is 22.8 tonnes, which is divided into the following components: structure, payload, propeller and kerosene-based propulsion system. The latter term includes a thermal engine per half-wing, the fuel (i.e., kerosene) and the relative storage system. The sizing consisted of calculating the number of stacks required for the FCS, the exchange area of the cooling system, and the mass of hydrogen required for the hydrogen tank.

The determination of the number of stacks involved a comparison between the required propulsive power, which is a function of the mission profile, and the net power generated by each individual stack as a function of the current and altitude, while considering the electro-mechanical efficiency of the electric motor. As the initial strategy, the nominal power (i.e., maximum power) of the stack was adopted as the designed working point for the sizing of the overall propulsion system. The calculation was conducted in steady-state conditions and for two distinct on-design points within the mission profile: the cruise and the take-off. The final on-design point of the fuel cell was determined by selecting the condition with the maximum number of stacks between the two mission phases. For the air compressor, the on-design point corresponds to the one where the maximum compression power is required. The hydrogen mass was calculated assuming a constant flow rate throughout the entire duration of the mission (two hours), and equal to the flow rate required during the cruise phase. This approximation is reasonable because the cruise phase typically occupies most of the flight time. The cooling system was designed considering the ϵ -NTU method for the calculation of the required exchange area.

A sensitivity analysis was conducted to determine the optimal working point of the fuel cell. The efficiency curve was used as the initial tool for the optimization process. The cruise stage was selected as the reference condition for this analysis because it is associated with the longest step of the mission in terms of duration. The following figure represents the system efficiency at the cruise stage, and two limiting working points were identified.

The first working point, denoted in red and located to the left, provides the maximum efficiency that determines the minimum weight of the hydrogen storage. On the other hand, the second working point, depicted in blue and positioned to the right, reflects the sizing approach that minimizes the number of stacks and leads to a power consumption at the cruise stage equal to almost 78 % of the nominal power. To the right of the blue point, it becomes evident that the number of stacks is inadequate to meet the maximum power demand of the aircraft during take-off. Conversely, to the left of the blue point the fuel cell system starts to be oversized, resulting in a weight increase; but this trade-off is accompanied by an improvement in the system efficiency until reaching the red dot. Subsequently, moving further to the left of the red dot, the efficiency experiences a decline, while the weight of the fuel cell system continues to increase. Operating the fuel cell system under such conditions is deemed infeasible. Hence, the optimal sizing point, which minimizes the overall weight of the propulsion system, was detected within the region situated between the two limiting points (the continuous black curve depicted in the figure) during the cruise stage.

The results obtained in this study reveal a noteworthy relationship between the sizing working point and the weight of the electrified propulsion system. In all examined scenarios, there is a consistent increase in the weight of the electrified propulsion system compared to the conventional kerosene-based one. However, the magnitude of this increase varies as the fuel cell is sized at different percentages of its nominal power. As can be seen in the following figure, for low operating points, a substantial oversizing of the number of stacks is observed, significantly impacting the overall weight of the electrified propulsion system.

Figure 5.4.6 – Weight distribution of the components of the electrified propulsion system for different off-design working points.

The weight of the stacks plays a pivotal role in determining the system's total mass at lower operating points. Conversely, for operating points near nominal conditions, the fuel cell exhibits its lowest efficiency. Consequently, the hydrogen storage and balance of plant components require larger sizes to compensate for this reduced efficiency. The optimal compromise between these two extreme conditions is found at intermediate operating points, notably at a working point of 50 %, which corresponds to approximately 64 % under on-design conditions. The analysis reveals that it is advantageous to oversize the number of stacks, ensuring that even under on-design conditions, the power output from the fuel cell is lower than the nominal rating. This approach allows for operation at higher stack efficiencies, leading to a reduction in the impact of components whose size depends on stack efficiency. Specifically, the cooling system benefits from lower heat generation, the compressor operates with reduced air flow rates, and the hydrogen storage system incurs lower hydrogen consumption due to enhanced stack efficiency. The trade-off between the number of stacks and their operational efficiency adds a layer of complexity to the optimization process. Achieving the right balance becomes imperative for maximizing the benefits of electrified propulsion while addressing weight constraints.

In conclusion, this work underscored that the feasibility of hydrogen-based fuel cell systems relies not only on hydrogen storage but especially on the electrochemical cell performance, which influences the size of the balance of plant and especially its thermal management section. In particular, the strategic significance of working with fuel cells at partial loads was demonstrated. This entails achieving an optimal balance between the stacks oversizing and the weights of both hydrogen storage and balance of plant, thereby minimizing the overall weight of the system. It was thus shown that an integrated approach is imperative to guide progress towards efficient and implementable hydrogen technology in regional aviation. Furthermore, a high-performance PEMFC was finally analyzed, resulting in an overall weight reduction up to nearly 10% compared to the baseline case study. In this way, it was demonstrated as technological advancements in PEMFCs can offer further prospects for improving system efficiency.

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Task 5.5 FC powered small hydrogen electric propelled boat (POLITO-DIMEAS)

One of the aspects that will characterize the electric boat powered by FC is the autonomous guidance. For instance, the boat will have a pre-programmed route, but must be able to avoid obstacles on the way also. For this purpose, the boat will be equipped with dedicated sensors and electronics to enable autonomous collision avoidance.

The most common way to enable environmental perception and obstacle detection on Autonomous Surface Vehicle (ASV) is vision. In particular, two types of sensors can be distinguished: i) RGB cameras, which permits to acquire color frames of the environment; ii) depth cameras (LiDAR), that give a representation of the observed scene in terms of a 3D point cloud.

While depth sensors are more reliable instruments to acquire distance data, RGB sensors can be combined with computer vision to recognize the type of obstacle. For this, the idea is to develop a sensor fusion architecture that merges signals from RGB cameras and depth cameras to enhance self-location of the boat and, more important, to track obstacles in the surrounding.

This part covers the development of a fundamental tool for autonomous guidance, that is the computer vision software for the classification of boats from RGB sensors. The problem is to recognize the boat type starting from RGB frames of the relevant environment of Venice canal. For the purpose, the following points have been studied:

- Sensor fusion architecture
- Image object detection

5.5.1 Sensor fusion high-level architecture

Different approaches for camera and LiDAR fusion can be found in the literature, such as Kalman Filter (KF) or Convolutional Neural Network (CNN).

For example, in [1] it is presented a traditional fusion strategy based on KF. In particular, the steps can be summarized in the followings:

1. Targets data acquisition: it consists in data collection through the ASV with the Camera and LiDAR.
2. Camera image processing: image object detection in images captured by camera with classification and boundary of targets. Also centroids are obtained and collected.
3. LiDAR frame processing: Segmentation and detection of the obstacle centroid in the point cloud.
4. Data association and transformation: to ensure that the same obstacle is being detected by the two sensors, and to transform to the same coordinate system.
5. Bayes Fusion: aims to create a better measurement with less noise.
6. Estimation Filter: obstacle path estimation using KF.

The previous example is fundamental to understand from a high point of view how to perform each step of a sensor fusion architecture between two sensors. However, an important aspect to emphasize is that, nowadays, the task related to the processing of the sensors data are based on Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) algorithms [2]. So, step 2 - Camera image processing and step 4 - LiDAR frame processing is strongly dependent on these kinds of algorithms.

In particular, object detection from camera image isn't an easy task because it is not known in advance how many objects will be in each input image and which is their dimensions. However, the advent of Deep Learning (DL) has revolutionized object detection methods, surpassing many traditional techniques in terms of both accuracy and speed.

In the realm of DL-based image object detection, a common approach employs a single network for both region prediction and label classification, as demonstrated by You Only Look Once (YOLO) algorithm [3]. In the case of YOLO, the input image is divided into coarse grids, and each grid is associated with a set of base bounding boxes. YOLO predicts offsets from the actual location, a confidence score, and classification scores for each base bounding box, indicating whether an object is present within that grid location.

In summary, from a high point of view, a fusion algorithm can be schematized as in Figure 5.5.1.1. Finally, the fusion algorithm gives the distance and the pose of a specific object.

The study of the sensor fusion architecture shows that, in general, image object detection is a fundamental step that is required to classify objects in the environment and to enhance obstacle tracking.

Figure 5.5.1.1 - Fusion system high-level block diagram

5.5.2. Image object detection

In order to perform object detection, it is necessary to have a data set. However, the literature lacks database on boats. To overcome this absence, the idea was to collect images from Google Earth Pro app, which allows to use street view also in Venice lagoon and save images in different resolution. The possibility to choose the resolution is relevant, because it permits to adapt the methodology on the camera that will be used on the boat. In this case, the Intel Real Sense D455 camera is considered, with a resolution of 1280x720, as it will most likely be used in the final prototype. However, the study and choice of sensors will be made at a later stage.

5.5.2.1. Data set analysis

Analyzing the data set of images, it was decided to try to recognize the boats dividing them in three different classes: waterbus, motorboat and gondola. Subsequently, the gathered images undergo processing using the MATLAB Image Labeler App, enabling the manual labeling of training images to identify objects belonging to distinct classes. It is important to understand that one should thereby pay attention to several possible issues that may be experienced by the dataset [4]. In particular:

- Scene Background: When images belonging to a particular object class consistently feature the same background scene, there is a risk that the system might end up learning the background more than the object itself.
- Forced Detection: When in each training image there is almost one object. It could comport that the detector learns to detect something in each test image although there is no object detectable.

Class Balance (inter-class): It is advisable to maintain a balanced count of images for each class, ensuring that each class has approximately an equal number of images. Otherwise, an issue known as class imbalance may arise. A straightforward approach to address this challenge involves implementing oversampling and under sampling techniques. Oversampling involves artificially generating new images for the class with fewer instances, often through augmentation methods. On the other hand, under sampling entails reducing the number of images in the class with a surplus of instances. AS in Venice Dataset there is a significant unbalance as shown in Figure 5.5.2.1.a, data augmentation can be applied. In particular, a custom function to augment images in Matlab was prepared, which considers random horizontal flipping, random scaling along the X and Y axes, as well as random color modification of the images.

- Objects Sizes Overlap (inter-class): for a good detector performance interclass overlap is essential. Figure 2b shows that this dataset is great from this point of view.

Intra-Class dimension variance: The choice of the better version of YOLO detector is strictly related to this issue. Figure 5.5.2.1.b illustrates an important variance in terms of dimensions in each class. This issue means that the detector must detect in different scales, so a multi-scale object detector is preferable to a single-scale detector.

Figure 5.5.2.1.2. a) Balance of the Venice data set; b) Dimension of the labelled objects.

5.5.2.2. Object detector analysis

During the frequency and dimensional analysis of the objects in the image dataset it was observed the inefficiency of the YOLOv2 because of low score confidence. As already mentioned, this is related to the fact that v2 is a mono-scale detector which performs better on specific object dimensions. For this reason, the Object detector YOLOv4 was chosen, which presents great performances in this case study. The in-depth analysis on the YOLOv4 architecture and details on its application can be found in [5].

The Object detector results are expressed throughout the important metrics: precision and recall:

- Precision is a measure of the accuracy of positive predictions made by a model. It is the ratio of true positive predictions to the total number of positive predictions (true positives TP, plus false positives FP). Thus, precision is defined as: $P=TP/(TP+FP)$. Precision tells us how many of the predicted positive instances are correct. A high precision indicates that when the model predicts an object, it is likely to be correct.
- Recall is a measure of the model's ability to identify all relevant instances in the dataset. It is the ratio of true positive predictions to the total number of actual positive instances (true positives TP, plus false negatives FN). Recall is defined as: $R=TP/(TP+FN)$. Recall tells us how many of the actual positive instances the model was able to find. A high recall indicates that the model can identify a significant portion of the positive instances.

5.5.3. Results

Figure 5.5.3.1 illustrates the precision-recall curve for each class. The average precision values demonstrate a commendable performance across all classes, with each class exhibiting a consistently high precision even as recall increases. Figure 5.5.3.2 shows a test image used to evaluate practically the detection.

For further studies, additional data can be collected, and a more detailed labeling effort can be undertaken to extend the data set.

Figure 5.5.3.1 - PR curves (a) Gondola, (b) Motorboat, (c) Waterbus.

Figure 5.5.3.2. Example of score detection and boat type classification for a Motorboat and a Waterbus

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Task 5.6 Analysis of the state of the art of dynamic gas journal bearings (POLITO-DIMEAS)

Overview on journal bearings test rigs

Most of the current turbomachinery applications uses rolling or oil lubricated bearings for rotor support. Although these conventional "oil-requiring" methods of supporting the rotor system have accomplished good reliability and performance, their maximum speed is limited due to inherent to physical stresses and power loss. Aircraft engines possess a DN speed limitation near 2.5 million due to the centrifugal loads on rolling elements, and machinery using oil-lubricated journal bearings is subject to significant power loss at high speeds [1]. Additionally, removing pumps and oil lubrication systems results in significant benefits: simplified design, reduction of the fuel consumption and weight.

Replacing rolling or oil bearings with aerodynamic bearings may be a good choice for different reasons. The weight of the system can be significantly reduced by eliminating oil lubrication system, pumps, seal and supply lines. Additionally, systems integrated with gas lubricated bearing technology require less maintenance thus becoming more reliable [2]. Since gas lubricants are not affected by cavitation phenomena, gas-lubricated systems can reach higher temperature and rotational speeds. Higher speed limits result in higher power density machines.

The most effective way to guarantee the reliability and performance of a bearing is to experimentally assess its features. The analysis of the literature makes it possible to distinguish two main test rig architecture: "floating" and "fixed" bearing configurations (see Figure below).

The fixed-bearing test rig configuration consists in a rigid rotor supported by two identical test bearings mounted at rotor extremities [3–6]. Static and dynamic loads are applied through a loading bearing usually located at the mid distance between the test bearings. This kind of solution can be a good choice when the main goal of experiments is to study the static and dynamic feature of the whole rotor-bearing systems [7]. Conversely, it presents different drawbacks when the main goal is the characterization of the bearings. In this case, mounting and dismounting operations can be very long and complicated since it is necessary to mount/dismount at least one of the tested bearings and successively verify the presence of possible shaft misalignment before any test.

The floating bearing test rig configuration [1,8–10] consists in a rigid rotor supported by two auxiliary bearings that are mounted at rotor extremities. The bearing under test is mounted in a housing located at the mid distance between the auxiliary bearings. Static and dynamic loads are applied on the housing of the test bearing while it floats on the rotor. Thanks to the presence of a single test bearing, the floating bearing design permits an ease application of dynamic loads by using shakers or piezoactuators acting directly on the housing and a relatively simple identification procedure. However, the use of this kind of configuration provides the test bearing with four degrees of freedom: two displacements (eccentricities along X and Y directions) and two rotations (pitching and yawing motions). These two rotations must be kept as small as possible since may affect the accuracy of the bearing characterization. For this reason, the test bearing is not mounted to be completely floating on the rotor, but it is constrained through stingers, cables [10] or squirrel cages [8].

The floating bearing test rig configuration can be further subdivided in straddle and overhung mounted configuration depending on the position of the test bearing with respect to the auxiliary ones (see Figure below).

The main difference between the overhung and straddle configuration regards the mounting/dismounting of the test bearing and the management of rotor misalignment due to the location where the external load is transmitted to the rotor. Regarding the rigid mode shapes of the rotor-bearing system, the straddle mounted design makes it possible to obtain a structure whose rigid mode shapes are more cylindrical than conical. The rotordynamic analysis of the rotor-bearing system is a crucial aspect since it makes it possible to identify the critical speeds of the system. When possible, it is preferable to have rigid auxiliary supports that guarantees that the first critical speed of the system is beyond the investigated frequency ranges. If this is not, to overcome in safe condition the critical speed, a flexible mounting of the auxiliary bearing is advisable.

Both floating and fixed bearing test rig configuration present pros and cons that must be suitably evaluated depending on the type bearing under test and the bearing features that have to be investigated.

Model of herringbone grooved journal bearings

This model is from paper [1]. The geometry of the herringbone is given by the following parameters:

- groove angle b
- relative groove width a
- relative groove depth H_0
- compressibility number L_s
- length-to-diameter ratio L/D

Here below is represented the geometry of the journal, of axial length L and diameter $D=2R$. The relative groove width is the ratio between the width of the groove and the width of the groove/ridge pair. Similarly, the relative groove depth is the ratio between the radial clearance in the groove and the radial clearance in the ridge. The compressibility number is a dimensionless parameter proportional to the rotational speed.

The goal of the model is to calculate the smooth pressure distribution depicted below, which approximates the real saw-toothed pressure profile occurring in the groove/ridge pair.

By writing the equations of the balance of mass in the groove and in the width and by imposing proper boundary conditions paper [11] derives the differential equation for the smoothed pressure \bar{P} :

$$L^2 \frac{C_1}{P_a} \frac{\partial^2 \bar{P}_1}{\partial z^2} + L \frac{C_2}{P_a} \frac{\partial \bar{P}_1}{\partial z} + L \frac{C_3}{P_a} \frac{\partial^2 \bar{P}_1}{\partial z \partial \theta^*} + \frac{C_4}{P_a} \frac{\partial \bar{P}_1}{\partial \theta^*} + \frac{C_5}{P_a} \frac{\partial^2 \bar{P}_1}{\partial \theta^{*2}} + C_6 \sin \theta^* + C_7 \cos \theta^* = 0$$

where coefficients C_1 to C_7 are a function of the herringbone geometry.

The boundary conditions are $\bar{P}(\theta^*, z) = 0$ at the edges of the journal bearing, that means that the absolute pressure is equal to ambient pressure. The final pressure distribution will be in the form

$$\bar{P}(\theta^*, z) = \bar{P}_0(z) + \epsilon \bar{P}_1(\theta^*, z)$$

as it can be seen as the sum of a term depending only on z and another term depending on the eccentricity ratio ϵ of the journal.

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Task 5.7 Development of a numerical model of bearings (POLITO-DIMEAS)

The design of the dynamic gas bearings able to sustain such systems up to very high speeds is very challenging. Numerical modeling of grooved bearings can be carried out either by discretizing the Reynolds equation or another simplified analytical model from the so-called Narrow Groove Theory (NGT), which neglects the pressure variation through the groove-ridge pair and assumes a mean pressure, with the advantage of obtaining the analytical expression for the pressure distribution [1]. Good agreement of the theory with experiments was found in [2].

The numerical analysis usually exploits either a Finite Difference (FDM) scheme or the Finite Element Method (FEM). The associated non-linear problem is solved with the Newton-Raphson procedure in [3] or with schemes based on the Galerkin method [4], [5].

For this analysis the RE is solved through a finite difference (FDM) scheme with mixed Dirichlet-periodic boundary conditions [6] within a computational domain that reproduces the film shape between the plates of a SGTB (see the figure below). Due to the symmetry of the problem, the RE is solved for within a period θ_p , as indicated below. The assumption of isoviscous, isothermal and incompressible fluid was applied because a limited air pressure increase is expected in hydrodynamic gas bearings.

For the numerical solution, the static Reynolds equation in polar coordinates is formulated in dimensionless form. Scaling of variables reduces truncation errors and makes the solution valid for multiple dimensional problems. Capital letters identify dimensionless quantities.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\frac{h^3}{12\mu_0} \frac{\partial p}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{h^3}{12\mu_0} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} \right) = \frac{r\omega}{2} \frac{\partial h}{\partial \theta},$$

$$\Omega_{r,\theta} = \{0 \leq \theta \leq \theta_p, r_1 \leq r \leq r_3\}$$

$$r_r R = r, \quad p_r P = p, \quad h_r H = h,$$

$$\frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(H^3 \frac{\partial P}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial R} \left(H^3 R \frac{\partial P}{\partial R} \right) = R \frac{\partial H}{\partial \theta},$$

$$(R, \theta) \in \overline{\Omega_{r,\theta}} = \{0 \leq \theta \leq \theta_p, R_1 \leq R \leq R_3\}$$

The FDM scheme converts the differential equation into a set of linear algebraic equations if the unknowns are reordered according to a lexicographic ordering of nodes [17]. $A^{NM \times NM}$ is eptadiagonal determining matrix, where the 1st, (N-1)th, and the Nth superdiagonals and subdiagonals are both non-zero due to the relationships between adjacent nodes of the computational grid. $P^{NM \times 1}$ is the solution in dimensionless form (dimensionless pressure distribution).

$$A^{NM \times NM} p^{NM \times 1} = f^{NM \times 1}$$

The load carrying capacity of the thrust bearing, according to equation

$$LCC = K \cdot \sum_e A_e \frac{(p_{SW} + p_{SE} + p_{NW} + p_{NE})_e}{4}$$

was calculated by numerical integration of the dimensional pressure distribution $p^{NM \times 1} = P^{NM \times 1} p_r$ across the computational domain. The area of the e^{th} element of the grid was calculated through equation

$$A_e = \Delta\theta(r_e + \Delta r) \frac{(r_e + \Delta r)}{2} - (\Delta\theta r_e) \frac{r_e}{2}$$

and the average of the pressure values at the nodes is associated to each element for higher accuracy (see figure below).

Likely dimension and operational conditions of the SGTB were considered for this analysis considering the characteristic and the target performance of the end prototype identified in Task 5.8, i.e. $r_3 = 20$ mm, $r_1/r_3 = 0.5$, rotational speed $w = 200$ krpm, and 6 to 20 grooves. The minimum air film thickness was assumed to be $h_2 = 5$ mm. The geometry of the bearing is state in terms of the dimensionless parameters X and Y , the spiral angle α , and the groove depth h_1 :

$$X = a_1/a_2, \quad Y = (r_3 - r_2)/(r_3 - r_1)$$

The value of these parameters to be used as input values to the numerical model was defined through an optimization procedure with the goal of maximizing the load carrying capacity (LCC). The NGT model by Muijderman [7] for the calculation of the pressure distribution inside the bearing was considered to carry out this preliminary optimization, and the optimized parameters thus identified are listed as follows:

$$X_{opt} = 1.576, Y_{opt} = 0.730, \alpha_{opt} = 71.6^\circ, \text{ and } h_{1,opt} = 20 \mu m.$$

The effect of the number of grooves on the LCC was investigated more in detail by solving the numerical model iteratively while increasing the grooves from $K = 6$ up to $K = 20$. The total number of nodes was kept constant and equal to $N, M = 220$ which is a compromise to avoid overly long time for computing each iteration. The figure below compares the geometry with 6, 13 and 20 grooves with same optimum geometric parameters while the next figure shows that the grooves have a considerable effect on the LCC which increases by 15% when the number of grooves is about 3 times larger. The figure also shows that when the number of grooves increases, the pressure distribution inside the thrust bearing approaches a torus with a quasi-triangular section, which justifies the simplifying assumptions considered by the NGTs.

Geometry and pressure distribution

- [1] 'On the Spiral Grooved, Self Acting, Gas Bearing'. Accessed: Mar. 11, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/citations/AD0433660>
- [2] R. E. Cunningham, D. P. Fleming, and W. J. Anderson, 'Experimental Load Capacity and Power Loss of Herringbone Grooved Gas Lubricated Journal Bearings', *Journal of Lubrication Technology*, vol. 93, no. 3, pp. 415–422, Jul. 1971, doi: 10.1115/1.3451610.
- [3] D. Bonneau and J. Absi, 'Analysis of Aerodynamic Journal Bearings With Small Number of Herringbone Grooves by Finite Element Method', *Journal of Tribology*, vol. 116, no. 4, pp. 698–704, Oct. 1994, doi: 10.1115/1.2927320.
- [4] N. Zirkelback and L. San Andre's, 'Effect of Frequency Excitation on Force Coefficients of Spiral Groove Gas Seals', *Journal of Tribology*, vol. 121, no. 4, pp. 853–861, Oct. 1999, doi: 10.1115/1.2834145.
- [5] P. Hernandez and R. Boudet, 'Modelling of the Behaviour of Dynamical Gas Seals: Calculation with a Finite Element Method Implicitly Assuring the Continuity of Flow', *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part J: Journal of Engineering Tribology*, vol. 209, no. 3, pp. 195–201, Sep. 1995, doi: 10.1243/PIME_PROC_1995_209_425_02.
- [6] A. Almqvist and F. P. Råfols, 'Scientific Computing with Applications in Tribology: A course compendium - Luleå University of Technology'. 2019.
- [7] E. A. Muijdermann, *Spiral Groove Bearings*. Springer-Verlag, 1966.

Task 5.8 Realization of a demonstrator (POLITO-DIMEAS)

The project aims to design and realize a demonstrator that shows the feasibility of supporting the rotor at about 200 krpm with dynamic gas journal bearings.

The specifications of the compressor to be sustained are defined as follows:

mass flow: 11.5 g/s
 pressure ratio: 1.3
 rotational speed: 200 krpm
 external tip diameter: 21 mm
 max electric power: 1 kW

In the demonstrator an idle impeller will be used, with the same mass and inertia characteristics of the compressor impeller.

Output and results:

We continued the analysis of Ultrasonic Spray Coating (USC) to deposit catalysts for the fabrication of PEM fuel cells, demonstrating a significant reduction of Pt loading. We patented a novel process based on CO2 laser writing to get LIG-based electrodes from Kapton membrane.

During the third reporting period, we investigate the effect of co-catalysis towards Oxygen Reduction Reaction, by decorating/modifying LIG-S surfaces with LIG-NFs.

We designed a new path for combining conventional hydrothermal/solvothermal synthesis with microwave-assisted methods.

Deviations (if applicable):

No deviations

Equipment and other direct external costs (goods, services etc) enabling research activities:

In order to perform the experimental tests on the high speed rotors, a capacitive measuring system CPL190 from Lion Precision has been purchased. In particular the system is comprehensive of 4 capacitance probes with 15 kHz bandwidth and sub-nanometer resolution. These sensors will be used to detect the radial vibration of the rotor on two measuring planes.

Objectives envisaged for the next reporting period:

During the next experimental steps, we will test the new LIG-Based electrodes with Pt/C deposited as catalyst layer.

Future research activities will be focused on testing the electrocatalytic behavior of LIG NFs in acidic media to mimic the typical environment of PEM Fuel Cells.

Results on microwave assisted synthesis of Heteroatoms-doped laser-induced graphene (LIG) materials and mesoporous Fe-N-C catalysts.

In the next reporting period we plan to give more details on the design of the test benches for the journal and thrust bearings.

Key Indicators for Research activities and Flagship Projects:

Action	Key Indicator	Flagship overall target	Flagship progress
Outcome	Number of Pilot Line / Demonstrators / Prototypes	2	2 in progress
	Number of publications	20 journal papers /publications in international conferences	14
	Number of registered IPR (patents, utility models, trademarks, industrial designs)	2	1 deposited 1 in preparation
Output	Number of professor and researcher involved	16	21
	Personnel effort dedicated to Research and Innovation and Flagship Project (person/month in three years)	146,5 PM	20,48

2. IMPACT

This first phase of the project has been mainly devoted to:

- the implementation of the management structure of the FP and the coordination of the different actors

involved

the final identification and set up of the research activities

The two expected prototypes are in progress.

14 articles have been published over the expected 20.

1 patent has been deposited and 1 is under preparation.

3. INDUSTRY PARTICIPATION AND INNOVATIONS (prototypes, clinical trials, Testing activities etc.)

The engagement of industry has been mostly linked to the involvement of the Stakeholders Committee. Moreover, the contents of the Flagship have been presented in different meetings with companies during the events for the launch of cascade calls. Meetings have been also organized by scientific coordinators with companies interested in the topics of the flagship. All the researchers involved in the FP are intensifying their research relationships with companies. To this end, they are establishing relationships with new companies and to identify topics of real interest where researchers' expertise may be of interest.

4. FOLLOW-UP OF RECOMMENDATIONS AND COMMENTS FROM PREVIOUS REVIEW(S) (IF APPLICABLE)

Not applicable

5. OPEN SCIENCE PRACTISES AND UPDATE OF THE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (IF APPLICABLE)

Three journal articles have been published under the Creative Commons (CC) license CCBY.

6. RESULTS BEYOND THE STATE OF THE ART

After a first phase of the project, mostly devoted to the set-up of the research activities, the recruitment of personnel and the revision of the state of the art, new advancement has been possible thanks to research activities performed so far within the project.

One patent has been deposited and 14 publications have been successfully presented and published.

ANNEXES

LIST OF DELIVERABLES

Add actual delivery dates (or new due date for late deliverables, together with an explanation for the delay). In the Comments, please indicate if the deliverable was achieved as planned or not.

The labels used mean:

Public — fully open; Sensitive — limited; R — Restricted; C — Confidential; S — Secret.

D. No	Name	RM No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)	Status	Comments
[number]	[name]	[RM Number]	[short name]	[R — Document, report] [DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype] [DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc] [DATA — data sets, microdata, etc] [DMP — Data Management Plan] [ETHICS] [SECURITY] [OTHER]	[PU — Public] [SEN — Sensitive] [R] [C] [S]	[month number]	[dd/mm/yyyy]	[dd/mm/yyyy]	[Pending] [Draft] [Submitted] ([Rejected] [Approved] [Removed])	[insert comments]
D1	H2Mobility Report 1	ALL	POLITO	R	PU	12				
D2	H2Mobility Report 2	ALL	POLITO	R	PU	24				
D3	H2Mobility Report 3	RM2 RM5	POLITO	DEM	PU	30				
D4	H2Mobility Report 4	ALL	POLITO	R	PU	36				

Table 1: Deliverables

LIST OF MILESTONES

Milestone No	Milestone Name	RM No	Lead Beneficiary	Means of Verification	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)	Achieved	Comments
[number]	[name]	[RM number]	[beneficiary short name]	[means of verification as in Annex 1]	[Month]	[dd/mm/yyyy]	[dd/mm/yyyy]	[YES] [NO]	[insert comment]
MS1	Milestone 1	ALL	POLITO	Issue of deliverable D1	M12				
MS2	Milestone 2	ALL	POLITO	Issue of deliverable D2	M24				
MS3	Milestone 3	RM2 RM5	POLITO	Issue of deliverable D3	M30				
MS4	Milestone 4	ALL	POLITO	Issue of deliverable D4	M36				

Table 2: Milestones

LIST OF CRITICAL RISKS

State of play: Give the state of play of the risks that were identified (and new risks that materialised during project implementation) and add new mitigation measures, if needed.

Risk No	Did you apply risk mitigation measures?	Did your risk materialize?	Comments
[risk number]	[YES] [NO]	[YES] [NO]	[insert comment (mandatory if no risk mitigation measures where applied or planned risk mitigation measures were not applied)]

Table 3: Risks

PROJECT PATHWAY TO IMPACT

Provide details about the project results. Please focus on the content of the results, for example discoveries and theories, products, services, methods etc. Publications, intellectual property rights, datasets, software, algorithms, protocols etc. will be linked to these results later in separate tables. It will also be possible to add these to the project as a whole.

Examples:

- The project developed a new medical device, which is described in two publications and later patented. Instructions: List the medical device here (as 'PROD: Product') and add publications to this product in dedicated sections. When you have information about the patent application, add it in a dedicated section.
- The project developed a new scientific theory which is described in several publications. Instructions: List the name and potential of the theory here (as 'SCI: Scientific discovery, model, theory') and add relevant publications later in dedicated sections.
- The project develops a high potential industrial process and is currently at the stage of prototyping. Instructions: List the industrial process here (as 'PROC: Industrial process') and indicate the prototyping stage under 'Steps undertaken towards exploitation'. If there is a registered prototype, add the registered prototype in a dedicated section.

Name	Result type	TRLs	Steps undertaken towards exploitation (multiple choice)	Market maturity (state of the market targeted by this result)
[name]	[SCI — Scientific discovery, model, theory...] [PROD — Product (new or improved)] [SERV — Service (new or improved)] [PROC — Industrial process (new or improved)] [BUS — Business model (new or improved)] [DSG — Design (new or improved)] [METH — Method, material, technology, design (new or improved)] [PO — Policy recommendation, guidance, awareness raising, advocacy] [EVNT — Event (conference, seminar, workshop)] [STAFF — (qualified personnel exchanges)] [LEARN — learning and training (learning modules, curricula)] [INFRA — new or improved infrastructures or facilities]	[TRL1- Basic principles observed] [TRL2- Technology concept validated] [TRL3 - Experimental proof of concept] [TRL4 - Technology validated in lab] [TRL5- Technology validated in relevant environment] [TRL6 - Technology demonstrated in relevant environment] [TRL7 - System prototype demonstration in operational environment] [TRL8- System complete and qualified] [TRL9 - Actual system proven in operational environment] [Not applicable]	[Prototyping in laboratory environment] [Prototyping in production environment] [Pilot, demonstration or testing] [Intellectual property management] [Complying with regulatory framework] [Contribution to standards] [Feasibility Study] [Market Study] [Business plan] [Other]	[Not yet existing and not clear if market can be created] [Market creating: not existing but potential for the creation of a new market] [Emerging: growing demand, scarce supply] [Mature: the market is already supplied with similar products]
CNR_ Participation	EVNT (Roma, 18-22 September 2023)	[Not applicable]	[Not applicable]	[Not applicable]

to Conference				
CNR _ Presentation to Spoke 1 financing opportunities for companies in the South	EVNT (Polytechnic of Bari, June 22 nd 2023)	TRL 6 - 7	[Not applicable]	[Not applicable]

Table 4: Results

PUBLICATIONS

Type of publication	Peer-review	Type of PID (repository)	PID of deposited publication	Link to publication (if no PID of publication)	Title of the publication (for book chapters: title of chapter not of book)	ISSN/eISSN (if book insert ISBN)	Authors	Title of the journal or equivalent	Number	Publisher	Month/Year of publication	Book title (if book chapter)	Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of	License type

													public atio n	
[Article in journal] [Publication in conference proceeding/ Workshop] [Book/ Monograph] [Chapter in book] [Thesis/ Dissertation] [Other]	[YES] [NO]	[DOI] [handle] [ARK] [URI] [pURL] [Other] [None]	[insert PID reference]	[insert link]	[insert title of publication]	[insert ISSN/eISSN number]	[insert author names]	[insert title of journal]	[insert number of journal]	[insert name of publisher]	[insert month of publication] [insert year of publication]	[insert book title]	[YES] [NO]	[CC BY or equivalent] [CC BY NC or equivalent] [CC BY ND or equivalent] [Other licences]
Conference	NO			https://www.nanoinnovation2023.eu/home/index.php/programme/workshops/ws-ii-sustainable-technologies	Development of proton exchange membranes using green solvents		E. Fontananova	NanoInnovation 2023	Workshop II: "Emerging materials and technologies for a sustainable"		2023			

									society "					
Article in journal	YES	10.1016/j.cattod.2023.01.030		CO2 hydrogenation to methanol over Zr- and Ce-doped indium oxide		Salomone F., Sartoretti E., Ballauri S., Castellino M., Novara C., Giorgis F., Pirone R., Bensaïd S.	Catalysis Today	423	Elsevier	2023				
Conference proceeding	YES	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-32439-0_35		Gas Bearings Applications in Automotive Fuel Cell Technology.		Colombo, F., Lentini, L., Raparelli, T., Trivella, A.	I4SDG Workshop 2023.	134	Springer, Cham.	2023				
Article in journal	YES	https://doi.org/10.3390/nano13222926		Ultrasonic Spray Coating to Optimize Performance of Bio-Electrochemical Systems		Spisni G., Massaglia G., Pirri F.C., Bianco S., Quaglio M.	Nanomaterials	13(22)	MDPI	2023				CC BY
Article in journal	YES	https://doi.org/10.3390/mi14122137		Microbial Fuel Cells as Effective Tools for Energy Recovery and Antibiotic Detection in Water and Food		Massaglia G., Spisni G., Pirri F.C., Quaglio M.	Micromachines	14-dic	MDPI	2023				CC BY
Article in journal	YES	https://doi.org/10.3390/nano13202801		A Nanofiber-Based Gas Diffusion Layer for Improved Performance in Air Cathode Microbial Fuel Cells		Massaglia G., Serra T., Pirri F.C., Quaglio M.	Nanomaterials	13/20	MDPI	2023				CC BY
Article in journal	YES	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2023.05.155		A metal hydride compressor for a small scale H2 refuelling station		J. Barale, F. Nastro, D. Violi, P. Rizzi, C. Luetto, M. Baricco	International Journal of Hydrogen Energy	48	Elsevier	2023				
Conference	NO		https://www.nanoinnovation2023.eu/home/index.php/programme/workshops/ws-ii-sustainable-technology	Materials for hydrogen handling		P. Rizzi	NanoInnovation 2023		Workshop II: "Emerging materials and technologies for a sustainable society "		2023			
Article in journal	YES	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.138141		Sustainable aviation fuel production using in-situ hydrogen supply via aqueous phase reforming: A techno-economic and life-cycle greenhouse gas emissions assessment		Pipitone G., Zoppi G., Pirone R., Bensaïd S.	Journal of Cleaner Production	418	Elsevier	2023				
[Article in journal]	[YES]	[DOI]	10.1515/pac-2023-1134	Hydrogen Storage and Handling with Hydrides	1365-3075	M. Baricco, E. M. Dematteis, J. Barale, F. Costamagna, M. F. Sgroi, M. Palumbo, P. Rizzi	Pure and Applied Chemistry	96	De Gruyter	2024				

Article in journal	YES		https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2023.109482	The potential of hydrogen-battery storage systems for a sustainable renewable-based electrification of remote islands in Norway		Trapani D., Marocco P., Ferrero D., Lindberg K. B., Sundseth K., Santarelli M.	Journal of Energy Storage	75	Elsevier	2024			
Article in journal	YES		https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0959652623041653	Optimal design of PV-based grid-connected hydrogen production systems		Marocco P., Gandiglio M., Santarelli M.	Journal of Cleaner Production	434	Elsevier	2024			
Article in journal	YES		https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydene.2023.10.202	Hydrogen evolution through ammonia borane hydrolysis over iron tailored pig manure catalyst		G. Gianola, M. Bartoli, C.F. Pirri, S. Bocchini	International Journal of Hydrogen Energy	51	Elsevier	2024			
Article in journal	YES		https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2024.118266	Optimal design of a hydrogen-powered fuel cell system for aircraft applications		Massaro, M. C., Pramotton, S., Marocco, P., Monteverde, A. H. A., Santarelli, M.	Energy Conversion and Management	306	Elsevier	2024			
Article in journal			https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2023.130559	Tailoring the acidity of ZSM-5 via surface passivation: Catalytic assessment on dimethyl ether to olefins (DTO) process		Giglio, Emanuele; Ferrarelli, Giorgia; Salomone, Fabio; Corrao, Elena; Migliori, Massimo; Bensaid, Samir; Pirone, Raffaele; Giordano, Girolamo	Fuel	362	Elsevier	2024			
Article in journal			https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2024.148902	Unravelling competitive adsorption phenomena in the aqueous phase reforming of carboxylic acids on Pt catalysts: An experimental and theoretical study		Pipitone, Giuseppe; Hensley, Alyssa J.R.; Omoniyi, Ayodeji; Zoppi, Giulia; Pirone, Raffaele; Bensaid, Samir	Chemical Engineering Journal	482	Elsevier	2024			
Article in journal			https://doi.org/10.1039/d3qj02499g	Development of In-Cu binary oxide catalysts for hydrogenating CO ₂ via thermocatalytic and electrocatalytic routes		Mezzapesa, Marco Pietro; Salomone, Fabio; Guzmán, Hilmar; Zammillo, Federica; Millini, Roberto; Bua, Letizia; Marra, Gianluigi; Tacca, Alessandra; Marrazzo, Rosamaria; Russo, Nunzio; Pirone, Raffaele; Hernández, Simelys	Inorganic Chemistry Frontiers	11 (8)	Royal Society of Chemistry	2024			

Table 5: Publications

DATASETS

Short Name:	
Description of datasets:	
Data origin:	
Data type:	
Data Formats:	
Useful for whom:	
If data is needed to validate conclusions of a scientific publication, describe the provisions whereby you intend to make it available	<p>[N/A] [open access given to data] [[other: please describe]]</p>
Findability (Type of PID, PID of deposited dataset):	<p>Persistent identifier and project metadata (provision of metadata and documentation) - URL to repository</p>
Accessibility:	<p>[Fully open à repository] [Partially open à repository and access methods] [no à motivation]</p>
Interoperability:	<p>Standards for interoperability</p>
Reusability:	<p>Licensing and restrictions, repository for long term preservation [CCBY or equivalent] [CCO or equivalent to CCO] [Other]</p>
Open	<p>[YES][Partially][NO] - Access methods</p>

Table 4: Data sets

INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS (IPRs)

Type of IP Rights	Application Title	Application Reference	Application Date	IPR Owner	IPR Status Has protection been awarded?	IPR Award Reference ID
[Patent] [Trademark] [Registered design] [Utility model] [Other]	[insert title of the application]	[OPTION for international applications of patents [insert IP international organisation code] [insert serial number]] [OPTION for national applications of patents [insert country code (two letters)] [insert serial number]] [OPTION for other registered IPR: [insert application reference country code (two letters) or organisation code]] [insert alpha numeric identifier]] [insert EPO/google patent format] [insert application ID]	[insert dd/mm/yyyy]	[insert owner name(s)]	[YES] [NO] [N/A]	[insert reference]
PATENT	PROCESSO DI REALIZZAZIONE DI ELETTRODI LIG	IT- N. 102024000001566	26/01/2024	POLITECNICO di TORINO	DEPOSITED	

Table 5: IPRs

OTHER RESULTS

Type of result	Description	If the result is needed to validate the conclusions of a publication, describe the provisions whereby you intend to make your output available, either in digital or physical form?	TRLs	Type of PID (if available)	PID (if available)	URL to repository landing page for the result service/webpage hosting the result (if available)	What license is the result under

[Software] [Workflow] [Protocol] [Prototype] [Other]	[insert description]	[N/A] [open access given to data] [[other: please describe]]	Expected by Project 'end: [TRL1- Basic principles observed] [TRL2- Technology concept validated] [TRL3 - Experimental proof of concept] [TRL4 - Technology validated in lab] [TRL5- Technology validated in relevant environment] [TRL6 - Technology demonstrated in relevant environment] [TRL7 - System prototype demonstration in operational environment] [TRL8- System complete and qualified] [TRL9 - Actual system proven in operational environment] [Not applicable]	[DOI] [handle] [ARK] [URI] [Other]	[insert PID reference]	[insert URL]	[CCBY or equivalent] [CC0 or equivalent to CC0] [Other]

Table 6: Other results

IMPACT in terms of TRLS, SDGs, KSOs

Technology readiness level of the project	
At project' start: [an item.]	Expected by Project 'end:
RM1 _ TRL 4	[TRL1- Basic principles observed]
RM2 _ TRL 4	[TRL2- Technology concept validated]
RM3 _ TRL 4	[TRL3 - Experimental proof of concept]
RM4 _ TRL 4	[TRL4 - Technology validated in lab]
RM5 _ TRL 4	[TRL5- Technology validated in relevant environment]
Current status: [an item.]	[TRL6 - Technology demonstrated in relevant environment]
No change	[TRL7 - System prototype demonstration in operational environment]
	[TRL8- System complete and qualified]
	[TRL9 - Actual system proven in operational environment]
	[Not applicable]

Table 7: TRLS

Is your project likely to deliver results relevant for the following Sustainable Development Goals?	
Climate neutrality	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Clean Water and Sanitation	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Life Below Water	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Life on Land	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
No Poverty	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Zero Hunger	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant]
	[Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Good Health and Well-being	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Gender Equality	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Decent Work and Economic Growth	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Affordable and Clean Energy	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Reduced Inequality	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]

Sustainable Cities and Communities	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Responsible Consumption and Production	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Quality Education	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Peace and Justice Strong Institutions	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
International cooperation	[Not relevant] [Partially relevant] [Full relevant] [Don't know (if nothing selected)]
Please explain your choice:	[insert text]

Table 8: SDGs

Horizon Europe KEY STRATEGIC ORIENTATIONS (KSO)	Horizon Europe Impact Areas	Contribution to the KSO and the relevant expected impacts
KSO 1 Promoting an open strategic autonomy by leading the development of key digital and enabling technologies, sectors and value chains to accelerate and steer the digital and green transitions through human-centred technologies and innovations	A competitive and secure data-economy	
	Industrial leadership in key and emerging technologies that work for people	
	Secure and cybersecure digital technology	
	High quality digital services for all	
KSO 2 Restoring Europe's ecosystems and biodiversity, and managing sustainably natural resources to ensure food security and a clean and healthy environment	Enhancing ecosystems and biodiversity on land and in waters	
	Clean and healthy air, water and soil	
	Sustainable food systems and nutrition security	
KSO 3 Making Europe the first digitally led circular, climate-neutral and sustainable economy through the transformation of its mobility, energy, construction and production systems	Climate change mitigation and adaptation	
	Affordable and clean energy	
	Smart and sustainable transport	
KSO 4 Creating a more resilient, inclusive and democratic European society, prepared and	A resilient EU prepared for emerging threats	

responsive to threats and disasters, addressing inequalities and providing high-quality health		
--	--	--

Table 9: KSOs and Impact Areas - HE